

Natural Melanin: A Multifunctional Biopigment for Advanced Biomedical Applications

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Abstract

Melanin, a widespread natural biopigment, has attracted growing attention owing to its multifunctional properties and potential in novel biomaterials. This review addresses the classification, biological sources, and extraction methodology of natural melanin from animals, plants, fungi, and bacteria, focusing on its physicochemical properties and bioactivities in therapeutic and diagnostic applications. Melanin's broadband ultraviolet (UV) and near-infrared (NIR) absorbance, strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, and photothermal conversion efficiency allow its incorporation in photothermal therapy, radioprotection, and wound healing platforms. Moreover, melanin's antimicrobial and antiviral activities that inhibit a diverse array of pathogens indicate its usefulness in surface disinfection and infection prevention. Current advancements in melanin-containing nanoformulations, hydrogels, and microneedle patches highlight their versatility in drug delivery, molecular imaging, and tissue regeneration. Importantly, eco-friendly extraction and utilization of natural melanin advance environmentally friendly approaches in the field of biomedical technology. This review highlights natural melanin's promise as a safe, biocompatible, and multifunctional agent, supporting its use in biomedical applications that address current healthcare challenges.

1. Introduction

Melanin is one of the oldest known natural pigments, with its presence and use dating back to the earliest forms of life on Earth, where it evolved as a crucial biological molecule to protect organisms from environmental stressors such as ultraviolet (UV) radiation and oxidative damage. The term *melanin* is derived from the Greek word *melanos*, meaning "dark." It was first applied in 1840 by Swedish scientist Jöns Jacob Berzelius to describe the dark pigment extracted from the eye membranes [1]. Beyond its protective role, melanin is deeply significant in medicine and science, being studied for its relevance to disease-related processes [2], immune functions [2,3], and its application in advanced diagnostic imaging and regenerative medicine [4–6].

The fundamental building blocks of melanin are indole-based units, which polymerize into complex, irregular macromolecular structures [1,7]. There are five main categories of melanin based on the chemical configuration of the polymer, namely eumelanin, pheomelanin, neuromelanin, allomelanin, and pyomelanin [8,9].

Melanin plays several diverse roles in nature, and its properties have been extensively studied. Its redox activity is attributed to quinone-based molecules, which enable dynamic electron transfer and radical scavenging capabilities [10–12]. As a broadband absorber, it provides effective UV shielding across UVA, UVB, and UVC spectra, thus playing a crucial role in photoprotection [13]. Moreover, its inherent biocompatibility support its safe integration into biological systems [14,15]. Melanin, especially that derived from fungi, is also increasingly studied for its robust shielding ability against gamma radiation [15]. This radioprotective function is attributed to melanin's capacity for free radical scavenging, physical

shielding, and efficient energy dissipation, as evidenced by the survival of melanized organisms in high-radiation environments [16,17]. Another notable feature is its photothermal conversion efficiency; upon near-infrared (NIR) light irradiation, melanin can convert absorbed photons into localized heat, making it a viable candidate for photothermal therapy (PTT) [18]. Beyond its role in photoprotection, melanin also exhibits potent anti-inflammatory properties [19,20]. Studies have shown that it can inhibit key inflammatory enzymes such as cyclooxygenase (COX) [21,22], and suppress activation of the nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) signal transduction pathway [23,24].

Recent research has demonstrated the utility of melanin in surface disinfection, particularly through its photothermal properties when combined with NIR lasers, enabling the eradication of bacteria via localized temperature increases [25–27]. Notably, naturally derived melanins themselves possess intrinsic antibacterial properties against a broad spectrum of bacterial strains, with studies showing efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) [28]. In addition to their antibacterial activity, certain melanins also exhibit antifungal effects against species (spp.) like *Candida albicans* (*C. albicans*) and filamentous fungi (e.g., *Aspergillus* (*A.*) spp., *Fusarium* (*F.*) spp.) [29,30], as well as antiviral potential against viruses such as HIV and SARS-CoV-2 [31].

The unique properties of melanin are driving an expanding array of biomedical technologies. It is increasingly being applied in developing advanced sunscreens and skin regeneration treatments [32,33]. Moreover, combined with other therapeutic modalities, synthetic and natural melanin nanoparticles are used in oncology for photothermal and chemotherapeutic treatments to heat ablate tumors with minimal off-target effects [34–36]. Melanin is also being applied in neuroprotective therapies for diseases such as Parkinson's by chelating metal ions and scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) due to its ability to quench oxy-radicals [37,38]. Other recent studies are exploring melanin-based scaffolds for tissue engineering applications, drug delivery systems that respond to stimuli [39,40], or as contrast agents for photoacoustic (PAI) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [41,42]. Recent technological advances have shown that multifunctional bioactive melanin can be integrated into biomedical devices.

Over the past two decades, research has increasingly focused on melanin-like nanoparticles, particularly polydopamine (PDA), a synthetic material that mimics natural eumelanin. As a result, comparatively less attention has been directed toward natural melanin, particularly in biomedical applications. Previous reviews have primarily emphasized the

biomedical applications of synthetic melanin [5,43,44]. While several excellent reviews on natural melanin exist [45,46], the present review distinguishes itself by focusing specifically on the biomedical applications of melanin derived from natural sources, including animals, plants, bacteria, and fungi. It provides a comprehensive summary of current extraction and preparation methods and offers a detailed overview of the key biological properties of natural melanin, such as its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiviral, and photoprotective activities. Furthermore, this review highlights its potential in various biomedical applications, including wound healing, tissue engineering, surface disinfection, cancer therapy, imaging, theranostics, targeted drug delivery, dietary supplementation, and the development of next-generation sunscreens.

2. Classification and sources of natural melanin

Natural melanin is responsible for pigmentation in humans, animals, and microbes, with colors ranging from dark brown to black and reddish to yellow, depending on the type. Melanin is commonly classified into five types based on their structural monomer composition and biosynthetic pathways: eumelanin, pheomelanin, neuromelanin, allomelanin, and pyomelanin (**Figure 1**).

Eumelanin appears dark brown to black and is one of the most abundant forms of melanin. It is found not only in human and animal hair, eyes, and skin, but also in numerous fungal species. It forms from the amino acid tyrosine through a series of steps involving the enzyme tyrosinase, which turns tyrosine into L-DOPA and then dopachrome. Later it is converted into the carboxylated 5,6-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (DHICA) and non-carboxylated 5,6-dihydroxyindole (DHI) monomeric units of eumelanin [8,45,46]. Its high efficiency in absorbing UV radiation makes eumelanin a critical photoprotective pigment [9].

Pheomelanin gives yellow to red tones in human hair, and is also present in people with fair skin, in bird feathers [47], and some insects [48,49]. Its production starts the same way as eumelanin but includes sulfur from the amino acid cysteine [45]. This change leads to the formation of cysteinyl-dopa, which undergoes cyclization to generate 1,4-benzothiazine intermediates. These intermediates can either retain or lose a carboxyl group before undergoing further polymerization to yield pheomelanin [50,51]. Unlike eumelanin, pheomelanin offers less protection against UV-induced damage and has been linked to increased susceptibility to phototoxicity [52].

Neuromelanin is a pigment composed of both eumelanin and pheomelanin, typically organized as a pheomelanin-rich core surrounded by eumelanin [51]. It is a black, insoluble pigment mostly abundant in human substantia nigra and locus coeruleus catecholaminergic neurons [53]. It is synthesized within neurons through the oxidative polymerization of catecholamines, primarily dopamine and norepinephrine, and their metabolites [54]. It has been proposed that neuromelanin plays protective roles by binding redox-active metal ions and mitigating oxidative stress, with implications for aging and neurodegenerative diseases [9,55,56].

Allomelanin is found in fungi, plants, and some bacteria. It is a dark, varied pigment that does not contain nitrogen and is produced through the 1,8-dihydroxynaphthalene (DHN) polymerization, starting from acetyl-CoA or malonyl-CoA [8,57]. It can also come from other compounds, such as catechol, dihydrofolic acid, and hyperic acid [51]. Functionally, allomelanin protects against environmental stress such as UV radiation, extreme temperatures, drought, and toxic chemicals [9,58,59].

Pyomelanin is a water-soluble pigment produced primarily by bacteria. Its biosynthesis starts with tyrosine, which is broken down to p-hydroxyphenyl pyruvate and then homogentisic acid (HGA) [60]. HGA is then secreted out of the cell, where it undergoes oxidation, forming benzoquinone acetate and self-polymerizes into pyomelanin [60,61]. Pyomelanin contributes to pigmentation and offers defense against oxidative damage [9,62,63].

Figure 1. Biosources of melanin.

2.1. Sources of melanin

Melanin is produced by a wide range of organisms, and its structure, function, and biosynthetic pathway are shaped by its biological origin. The following sections discuss the major sources of natural melanin, including animals, plants, fungi, and bacteria, with an emphasis on their extraction yield. However, reported yields do not reflect the chemical purity of the melanin, which can vary significantly depending on the source material and extraction method used. Moreover, the presence of other components during extraction can negatively impact melanin purity. Consequently, purification efforts are crucial, as they ultimately determine the quality and industrially relevant yield of melanin [60].

2.1.1. Melanin in animals

Melanin is present in various animals. In humans, it is found in skin, hair [64,65], as well as in the brain, where neuromelanin is located in regions of the substantia nigra. The amount of melanin in human hair varies, but it's typically around 1-4.8% of the hair's weight [64,66]. The quantity of melanosomes in hair is correlated with hair color; light-brown hair contains approximately 3.95% melanin by weight, whereas black hair contains up to 4.8% [64]. That black pigment is also found in the hair and fur of other mammals, such as horses, alpacas, and yaks [28,67,68].

Cephalopod ink, particularly from octopus, cuttlefish, and squid, is recognized as a highly abundant source of melanin [69], with the pigment occurring as small, spherical nanoparticles [70]. Notably, cuttlefish ink (*Sepia esculenta*) can yield up to 87.1% melanin when using water extraction methods, which are superior in preserving the indole structure and morphology of the pigment compared to enzymatic or acid-based extractions [71]. Similarly, Abidin et al. reported melanin yields from squid ink (*Loligo sp.*) ranging from 63.0% to 84%, depending on the extraction solvent [72].

Insects provide another, less-studied source of melanin. A recent patent has demonstrated an efficient method for extracting melanin from the arthropoda phylum species, including *Hermetia illucens* and *Tenebrio molitor* [73]. Chen et al. recently demonstrated the feasibility of scaling up the sequential extraction of eumelanin from defatted black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) biomass. By optimizing enzymatic hydrolysis and extraction conditions, the researchers were able to convert 50 kg of substrate into 0.85 kg of melanin in a pilot-scale trial, yielding 1.7%, which shows potential for industrial-scale production [74]. Butterfly wings have also been identified as a source of melanin, with pigment synthesis regulated by melanogenesis pathways [75].

Melanin is also a key pigment in bird feathers, where it primarily produces coloration and, through its structural arrangement, influences light absorption and reflection [76]. It is widely distributed in the feathers of many bird species, including crows [77] and various birds of prey such as Harris's hawks, red-tailed hawks, kestrels, and barn owls [78].

Additionally, Kalinina et.al. confirmed the presence of melanin in various animals belonging to the Canidae family, such as raccoon dogs (*Nyctereutes procyonoides*), foxes (*Vulpes spp.*), and Arctic foxes (*V. lagopus L.*). The pineal gland pigmentation was mainly localized around blood vessels and at the gland periphery, with notable species and age-related variations [79].

2.1.2. Melanin in plants

Allomelanin is the main type of melanin found in plants and plays a key role in their pigmentation. Notably, it has been reported in significant amounts (1.2-5.1%) in date palm fruits (*Phoenix dactylifera L.*), as documented by Alam et al. [80]. Another study reported the isolation of allomelanin from black garlic [81]. A study by Aghajanyan et al. isolated melanin from various plant sources, reporting yields of 21.5% from grape peel, 18.3% from black tea, 13.2% from coffee, 7.5% from banana peel, and 6.7% from sunflower seed husks, using a simple, solvent-free extraction method [82]. Additionally, the same research group identified the residual material from wine production as a novel source of water-soluble melanin, reporting a yield of 17.3% [83].

Dark seed pigmentation is a common feature among many plant species and is largely attributed to the accumulation of melanin-type pigments in seed coats. This has been demonstrated through physicochemical and spectroscopic analyses in various crops, including chestnut (*Castanea mollissima*), oat (*Avena sativa*), sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*), watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*), grape (*Vitis vinifera*), ipomoea (*Ipomoea purpurea*), sesame (*Sesamum indicum*), rapeseed (*Brassica napus*), and black mustard (*Brassica nigra*) [84].

Chestnut shells (*Aesculus hippocastanum*) contain a high reported melanin concentration, up to 24.5% by weight [85]. Black-seeded sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) contains melanin in the amount of 95.8-105.5 mg/g, yielding 9.6-10.6%, while brown-seeded cultivars of the same species contain 51.3-76.5 mg/g, resulting in a concentration of 5.1-7.7% [86]. The melanin content in sunflower husks averages 5.7% [87], whereas nigerseed (*Guizotia abyssinica*) hulls supply about 5 g per kg on a dry weight basis, meaning a 0.5% yield [88].

Lastly, melanin has also been isolated and characterized from watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) seeds, although yield data were not specified [89].

2.1.3. Melanin in fungi

In fungi, melanin is typically concentrated in the cell wall or secreted outside the cell as granules or fibrils [7,90], where it serves as an effective shield against various environmental stresses [90]. Quantitative studies have reported considerable variation in melanin yields among different fungal species. *Spissiomycetes endophytica* serves as a potent source and can produce as much as 315.2 mg of melanin per gram of dried biomass, equivalent to 31.5% w/w [91], whereas Chaga mushrooms offer a melanin yield of around 14.5% [82]. Around 10% of melanin has been extracted from Black knot (*Apiosporina morbosa*) relative to its dry biomass [58], while *Sporisorium reiliana* has been reported to yield around 3.5% [92]. Meanwhile, the extraction of pigment from oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus cornucopiae*) yields both eumelanin and pheomelanin, providing 11 mg of pigment for every gram of mushroom tissue, which corresponds to 1.1% w/w [93]. *Armillaria cepistipes* has eumelanin output reaching as much as 28 g/L, resulting in a 2.8% w/v yield [94]. In comparison, black yeast *Hortaea werneckii*, which thrives in salty conditions, can produce 5.6 g/L, meaning 0.56% w/v, of eumelanin after 168 hours of cultivation [95]. Other notable examples include *Thermothelomyces hinnuleus*, with up to 28.3 mg per 100 mL of culture broth, equivalent to 0.0283% w/v [96]. Recently, melanin was also extracted from another edible mushroom such as *Lentinus edodes* (shitake mushroom) [97].

2.1.4. Melanin in bacteria

Microbial melanin, owing to its low production costs, minimal growth requirements, and sustainable production processes, represents a highly promising source for biotechnological applications [98]. Several bacteria stand out as particularly efficient melanin producers, each with distinct yields and production dynamics. For example, *Streptomyces kathirae* has been reported to accumulate up to 13.7 g/L, meaning 1.37% w/v, of eumelanin over 128 hours; however, achieving this high yield requires prolonged fermentation with tyrosine supplementation [99]. In contrast, fast-growing species such as *Pseudomonas stutzeri* and *Bacillus safensis* can rapidly produce high melanin yields (over 6.7 g/L, equal to 0.67% w/v, in 10 hours) without tyrosine supplementation, using seawater or fruit waste extract as substrates [98,100,101].

Moreover, recombinant *E. coli* expressing the 4-HPPD gene yields 315.5 mg/L (0.03155% w/v) pyomelanin in 24 hours, achievable through genetic engineering [98,102]. Similarly, pyomelanin production by key enzyme 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate dioxygenase (4-HPPD) has been demonstrated in *Ralstonia picketti*, which produces 90.9 mg/L, equivalent to 0.00909% w/v, in 60 hours in the presence of tyrosine [98,102]. Additionally, a recent study by Liu et al. genetically engineered *Bacillus thuringiensis* to biosynthesize melanin, enabling its use as a multifunctional agent for anti-tumor and anti-inflammatory cancer therapy [103].

3. Extraction strategies for melanin

Melanin extraction depends on the source, such as animals, plants, fungi, or bacteria, as well as the type of melanin, its solubility, and binding properties. The process involves cell disruption, isolation and purification. Common techniques include chemical methods like alkaline or acidic hydrolysis, enzymatic extraction, and solvent use. Modern approaches include ionic liquids, ultrasonic treatment, and microwave-assisted extraction.

3.1. Acid/Alkaline extraction

Melanin is a negatively charged polymeric molecule, insoluble in water and acid [104], and it is tightly bound to tissues or cell walls, making its isolation challenging. Therefore, most extractions are performed in an alkaline environment using sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium hydroxide, or ammonium hydroxide, typically through reflux in a water bath or autoclaving [105]. As reported by Singla et al., melanin was extracted by dissolving black-knot fungus in NaOH under autoclave conditions, followed by centrifugation and precipitation with hydrochloric acid (HCl) until the solution reached pH 1. Finally, the precipitate was washed with water and lyophilized [58]. Aghajanyan et al. reported an 11-12% reduction in melanin yield from grapes when samples were autoclaved, compared to non-autoclaved controls [106].

In a separate investigation, Wang et al. isolated melanin from black garlic paste using an alkali-based extraction method involving dissolution in NaOH, autoclaving, centrifugation, and precipitation with HCl. After washing, the precipitates were air-dried [81]. Similarly, Sunil Kumar et al. explored melanin extraction from nigerseed hulls by employing NaOH to solubilize pigment, followed by acid precipitation with pH adjustment to 2. The obtained melanin exhibited promising antioxidant and antibacterial properties [88].

3.2. Enzymatic techniques for melanin isolation

Enzymatic methods for melanin extraction have gained increasing attention as environmentally friendly and less aggressive alternatives to conventional chemical techniques. Within this framework, Wen Song et al. extracted melanin from squid ink using alkaline protease enzymes. The extraction rate, melanin purity, and hypoglycemic activities were compared with those obtained in the alkali-acid precipitation method. The enzymatic extraction yielded 88.3% eumelanin with a purity of 91.6%, whereas the alkali extraction yielded 16.8% and a purity of 58.6% respectively. Additionally, the effect of enzymatic-assisted extraction on the inhibition of α -amylase and α -glucosidase was better than that of alkali-assisted extraction [107].

Another study by Song et al. examined the extraction of melanin from squid ink using seven enzymes, including optimization of single-, double-, and triple-enzyme extraction processes. This research focused not only on selecting appropriate enzymes but also used response surface methodology (RSM) to optimize the enzymatic extraction of melanin. As a result, three enzymes, alkaline protease, neutral protease, and flavour protease, demonstrated the highest extraction rates [108]. According to Wen Song et al., melanin extracted from squid ink using a complex enzyme extraction method, particularly alkaline-neutral-flavor protease, demonstrated a superior inhibitory effect against α -glucosidase and α -amylase, while increasing glucose uptake and glycogen synthesis in the insulin resistance model of human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line (HepG2) [109].

3.3. Green and eco-friendly extraction approaches

Recently, a novel method was developed to extract melanin from various sources using ionic liquids (ILs) or deep eutectic solvents. These solvents, prepared with quaternary ammonium compounds, interact strongly with eumelanin due to the presence of carboxylic and indole groups in its structure. For example, Vishal et al. reported a method that uses an IL, such as tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAOH, 40% w/w in H₂O), as a solvent to extract melanin from the microbial endophyte *Streptomyces hyderabadensis* 7VPT5-5R. In this research, the authors first harvested microbial culture from an 8-day-old broth, then centrifuged and lyophilized the sample. Water and TBAOH were added to facilitate extraction. Then, ethyl alcohol was added to the sample mixture to aid in the evaporation of water via rotary evaporator, increasing the yield of melanin up to 66% in comparison to the conventional method of extraction [110]. In a similar approach, Nirpat Singh et al. employed the same 40% TBAOH solution to extract melanin from human hair waste. This method enabled the simultaneous extraction of melanin, yielding 20-22%, and keratin, yielding 36-38%, while

preserving the structural integrity of both biomolecules. Additionally, the residual biodegradable IL contained 6.99% nitrogen [111]. Hair-derived melanin was also extracted by Mukherjee et al. (2023) using ionic liquids. The study employed 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([BMIM]Cl) as the extraction medium. This method yielded 17-17.8% melanin and 11.2-15.2% keratin, while preserving the functional properties of both biopolymers [112].

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is another method based on an eco-friendly approach, posing no harmful effects on the environment. UAE works on the principle of the thermal effect, the cavitation effect, and the mechanical impact, generating high-frequency sound waves to create localized heat and pressure to disrupt cell walls and enhance the release of target compounds [113,114]. In the study by Ming Lu et al., researchers examined how UAE affects melanin recovery from *Sporisorium reilianum* (*S. reiliana*). They used both single-factor tests and RSM to optimize the process. A Box-Behnken design helped assess the impact of four factors: ultrasonic power, extraction time, temperature, and the pH of the NaOH solution. The best results were achieved with 245 W ultrasonic power, a temperature of 50 °C, 2 hours of extraction, and NaOH at pH 13. Under these conditions, the melanin yield reached 3.52%, which was very close to the predicted value. In addition to improved extraction efficiency, the melanin extracted via UAE demonstrated notable bioactivity, particularly the antiproliferative effect. It exhibited a significant inhibitory effect against α -glycosidase and PTP1B with IC₅₀ 82.16 ± 5.02 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 81.27 ± 10.48 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively [92].

Similarly, Ruolin Hou et al. investigated the extraction of melanin from *Inonotus hispidus* using UAE, optimizing the process through RSM. The optimal extraction conditions were determined to be 0.56 mol/L NaOH, a solid-to-liquid ratio of 1:50, ultrasonic power of 300 W, extraction temperature of 70 °C, and ultrasonic time of 70 minutes. Under these conditions, the predicted melanin yield was 33.03%, while the experimental yield reached $33.29 \pm 0.29\%$, confirming the accuracy and reliability of the model. Furthermore, a comparison with a non-ultrasound control group, which yielded $24.24 \pm 0.36\%$, it demonstrated a 37.33% increase in extraction efficiency due to ultrasound application [115].

In addition to these green extraction methods, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) has emerged as an effective and environmentally sustainable technique for melanin isolation. MAE employs microwave energy to heat polar solvents and sample matrices via dipole rotation and ionic conduction, resulting in internal vapor pressure that ruptures cell walls and releases target compounds rapidly [116,117]. For instance, Ying Lu et al. extracted melanin from *Lachnum singerianum* YM296 using the optimized conditions of MAE (1.05 mol/L NaOH, solid-liquid ratio 1:14.72 g/mL, 118.70 seconds, 320 W), achieving a high yield of 11.08%,

which was approximately 40.43% higher than that of extraction by alkali extraction and acid precipitation [118]. More recently, Yinpeng Ma et al. optimized MAE conditions for extracting melanin from *Auricularia heimuer* fermentation. The optimal conditions included an alkali-soluble pH of 12.3, an acid precipitation pH of 3.1, and a microwave time of 53 minutes, resulting in a melanin yield of 0.4042% [119]. A comparative overview of various melanin sources, extraction methods, and their respective advantages and disadvantages is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Melanin sources and extraction techniques: advantages and limitations

Sources of melanin	Method of extraction	Advantages	Disadvantages
Grape pomace [106], black knot fungus [58], <i>S. reiliana</i> [92], black garlic [81], sepia ink [81], nigerseed hulls [88].	Chemical-based Extraction Method	Cost-effective, convenient [58], can be combined with an ultrasound-assisted technique [92].	Low extraction efficiency [107], time-consuming [120], may destroy the polymer structure [105], require multiple steps, use corrosive solvents, and have no reusability [110]. environmental pollution risk, not conducive for large-scale [9].
Silky fowl [121], human hair [122], cuttlefish ink [107], squid ink [108].	Enzymatic extraction	Eco-friendly, milder treatment, high purity, structural integrity [122], high yield [107], and extract uniform melanin particles, digest protein, hydrolyse protein strongly linked to melanin [9].	High cost [120], time-consuming [110], needs heating [9], sequential digestion steps with multiple specific enzymes [68].
Chaga mushroom extract [123], <i>Streptomyces hyderabadensis</i> 7VPT5-5R [110], <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> [124]. human hair [112,125], <i>Inonotus hispidus</i> mushroom [115], <i>Lachnum singerianum</i> YM29 [118], <i>Auricularia heimuer</i> [119].	Green and Eco-friendly approaches	Reusable solvents, no environmental effects, high yield, and purity, fast and straightforward [9], one-pot, can be used for large-scale extractions [110], save energy, reduce the use of solvents, and achieve high extraction efficiency [9].	High cost, ultrasonic treatment may alter the melanin structure [9], uneven heating system in microwave radiation [9].

4. Physicochemical and biological properties of natural melanin

4.1. Antioxidant properties

The antioxidant characteristics of melanin pigment are among its many important biological characteristics. Acting as both an electron donor and acceptor, melanin carries out one-electron transfer processes that enable it to neutralize free and peroxide radicals [126,127]. The antioxidant properties of melanin in marine organisms, especially cephalopods, have been the subject of numerous studies [128]. Melanin extracted from cuttlefish and octopus ink sacs was studied by Shaju et al. The study aimed to evaluate its antioxidant properties using the stable 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical, a standard probe for assessing free-radical scavenging activity; however, substantial methodological variability across DPPH protocols (e.g., solvent system, concentration, incubation time) limits inter-study comparability. Melanin extracted from octopus ink demonstrated the DPPH scavenging activity, reaching 28.29% at a concentration of 0.045 mg/mL [129]. In another study, melanin extracted from cuttlefish ink exhibited 50% scavenging activity at a concentration of 99.8 µg/mL [71]. Melanin extracted from squid ink demonstrated a maximum DPPH scavenging activity of 63.21% at a concentration of 5 mg/mL [128]. In a study by Le et.al, the mechanism of the antioxidant properties of melanin from cuttlefish ink on Clone-9 cells was investigated (**Figure 2a**). The results demonstrated that melanin treatment significantly reduced intracellular ROS levels while enhancing mitochondrial membrane potential. Additionally, melanin upregulated the expression and activity of key antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx). The study concluded that this protective capacity was mediated by activation of the nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) transcription factor, leading to its translocation from the cytoplasm to the nucleus [130].

Melanin extracted from plants and fungi has also been investigated for its antioxidant properties. Fu et al. examined *Sporisorium reiliana*, an edible fungus commonly used in traditional Chinese medicine. At a 0.5 mg/mL concentration, melanin had a DPPH scavenging rate of 72.35%. Additionally, no cytotoxic effect on HepG2 cells was observed at melanin concentrations of 10-400 mg/L. More importantly, *in vitro* studies of antioxidant melanin from fungus showed significant protection of HepG2 cells against H₂O₂-induced damage. At 400 mg/L, cell viability reached 85%, which is 15% higher than that of the H₂O₂ injury model group [131]. Similarly, melanin extracted from nigerseed has also demonstrated antioxidant potential, exhibiting 77.58% scavenging activity at a concentration of 5 mg/mL [88]. Melanin derived

from marine *Streptomyces* spp. showed antioxidant potential, exhibiting 93.47% scavenging activity at a concentration of 150 µg/mL [132]. At a concentration of 40 µg/mL, melanin extracted from black garlic exhibited a DPPH scavenging activity of 57.8% [81].

According to Simon et al., the antioxidant properties of complex melanins arise primarily from the eumelanin component, whereas pheomelanin tends to promote oxidative activity. As a result, melanin does not exhibit a purely antioxidant or pro-oxidant character, but rather reflects a balance shaped by the relative amounts of each component. In biological systems, however, this balance tends to favor antioxidant activity, since eumelanin is usually the predominant type present in tissues [133].

4.2. Anti-inflammatory properties

Numerous studies have demonstrated that natural melanin may regulate cytokine production and enhance various immunological indicators, highlighting its potential importance in modulating inflammation, a key factor in many chronic illnesses [20–22,27,134–138]. The anti-inflammatory activity of melanin produced from microbial populations extracted from insects was described by Barretto et al., who reported that melanin from *Cryptococcus rajasthanensis* significantly inhibited heat-induced protein denaturation [135]. This action can be attributed to the presence of phenolic groups in melanin, which modulate pro-inflammatory gene expression through NF-κB and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways while activating the Nrf2/Kelch-like ECH associated protein 1 (Keap1) pathway [135].

In a separate study, Liu et al. found that melanin from *Sepia pharaonis* ink protected mice against ethanol-induced gastric ulcers. Histological analysis showed that squid melanin significantly reduced the ulcerated area compared to mice exposed to ethanol alone. Although melanin demonstrated antioxidant activity, it more importantly inhibited pro-inflammatory cytokines: tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-1β (IL-1β). It also suppressed the protein expression of toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), p38 MAPK, and extracellular signal-regulated protein kinases 1/2 (ERK1/2). Squid melanin also kept gastric cells alive by lowering Caspase-3 expression and thus blocking apoptosis [138]. Similarly, Zu et al. demonstrated the anti-inflammatory activity of melanin nanoparticles in MRI-guided atherosclerosis treatment by reducing pro-inflammatory cytokine levels and additionally downregulating canonical pyroptosis-related proteins, including nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-like receptor (NLR) family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), Caspase-1, and Gasdermin D (GSDMD) [136].

Figure 2. Key characteristics of natural melanin: antioxidant, antibacterial, UV-protective, and radioprotective. a) Effects of cuttlefish ink melanin on oxidative stress in Clone-9 cells via Nrf2 pathway activation. Reproduced with permission [130], Copyright 2024, Elsevier Ltd. b) Antibacterial and antifungal activity of melanin pigment produced by *Curvularia soli* against bacterial strains (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K. pneumoniae*)) with ampicillin as a positive control (top row), and antifungal activity against eight fungal strains (*A. brasiliensis*, *A. niger*, *A. sydowii*, *A. candidus*, *A. parasiticus*, *P. notatum*, *F. oxysporum*, *P. digitatum*) with nystatin as a positive control (bottom two rows). Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [139], Copyright 2024, The Authors. c) Extraction and purification of melanin from *Pseudomonas* sp. and its photoprotective effects against UV-B-induced ROS generation in NIH 3T3 cells, showing minimal ROS generation upon UV-B irradiation compared to untreated cells. Reproduced with permission [140], Copyright 2021 Elsevier B.V. d) Protective effect of nanomelanin extracted from squid ink on human fibroblasts (hFB) cell viability against X-ray irradiation. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [15], Copyright 2024, The Authors.

4.3. Antimicrobial properties

Several studies have explored the antimicrobial activity of melanin derived from natural sources [28,30,88,134,139,141–144]. For instance, melanin produced by *Cryptococcus rajasthanensis*, isolated from the gut of the insect *Bombyx mori*, exhibited inhibitory effects

against *S. aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* (*B. subtilis*), *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. Atomic force microscope analysis further confirmed this antimicrobial activity by revealing disrupted cell integrity in these pathogens [135]. As shown in **Figure 2b**, melanin extracted from *Curvularia soli* demonstrated strong antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *K. pneumoniae*, with minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values ranging from 6.25 to 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and showed greater efficacy against gram-negative bacteria. Melanin displayed dual behavior, serving as bacteriostatic at lower concentrations and bactericidal at higher ones. In terms of antifungal activity, it showed the highest inhibitory effects against *Penicillium digitatum* and *F. oxysporum*, with inhibition zones of 44.25 ± 0.21 mm and 43.58 ± 0.16 mm, respectively. Moderate effects were observed against *A. brasiliensis*, *A. niger*, *A. sydowii*, *A. candidus*, *A. parasiticus*, and *Penicillium notatum* [139]. Melanin extracted from fungi like *Fomes fomentarius* and *Daedaleopsis tricolor* demonstrated antibacterial activity against *Cutibacterium acnes*, an acne-causing bacterium [141]. Lastly, *Actinoalloteichus cyanogriseus* from marine soil produced 2.5 mg/mL of extracellular black melanin with antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* (MIC 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) [142].

Recent attention has turned toward nigerseed (*Guizotia abyssinica*), with successful extraction of melanin from its hulls reported by Sunil Kumar et al. [88]. The melanin extract displayed notable antibacterial activity against foodborne pathogens, with inhibition zones (mm) observed as: *Salmonella enterica* (40.0), *S. aureus* (37.3), *Micrococcus luteus* (31.7), *Klebsiella oxytoca* (31.3), *E. coli* (30.3), and *Bacillus cereus* (28.3). Additionally, the melanin extract exhibited selective antifungal activity, indicating its potential as a targeted antifungal agent. These findings position nigerseed byproducts as a cost-effective and viable source of melanin for pharmaceutical applications [88].

Biowaste from wine production is a promising source of plant-based melanin with potential for biomedical and food preservation uses. The utility of melanin extracted from wine waste was demonstrated by Minasyan et al., who evaluated its antimicrobial properties for potential biopreservation applications [30]. In their study, water-soluble melanin isolated from grape peels exhibited strong antibacterial effects, particularly against *B. subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, and *C. bovina*, while showing bacteriostatic effects on *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium*. At concentrations of 20-40 mg/mL, melanin significantly reduced cell counts of test bacteria and yeast in a time- and dose-dependent manner, with near-complete inhibition of *B. subtilis* and *C. gropengiesseri* at 40 mg/mL. Additionally, melanin displayed fungistatic activity against various food spoilage fungi, including *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* spp. Its thermal stability,

acid resistance, and biocompatibility underscore its potential as a natural alternative antimicrobial agent [30].

Additionally, melanin extracted from *Sepia* sp. exhibited strong antibacterial activity against *Aeromonas* sp., causing over 99% reduction in viable colonies at 10 mg/mL within 24 hours. Transmission electron microscopy analysis in this study showed that the treatment prolonged the bacterial adaptation phase, accelerated cell death, and increased cell wall permeability. Higher melanin concentrations led to greater cell leakage, evidenced by increased OD at 260 nm and 280 nm, confirming membrane damage and melanin penetration into bacterial cells [143].

Horsehair has recently been investigated as an antibacterial agent by Rahmani et al., who reported that melanin extracted from *Equus ferus* hair exhibits a homogeneous elliptical microstructure with ordered semicrystalline features. Spectroscopic analysis revealed a high content of redox-active catechol groups capable of generating ROS. Incubation with *E. coli* and *S. aureus* resulted in 100% bacterial growth inhibition within 4 hours, indicating that horsehair-derived melanin can act as a potent, naturally sourced antibacterial agent [28]. Other studies have also highlighted melanin's pro-oxidant potential [10,145]. Kim et al. demonstrated that its activity depends on redox state, which is influenced by environmental factors, showing that melanin can function as a reductant when quenching radicals or as an oxidant when transferring electrons to oxygen and generating ROS [10]. In addition, the antibacterial effects of melanin against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria may be influenced by differences in their cell wall structures [30].

Moreover, a novel antimicrobial strategy has been developed using melanin's photothermal properties to kill bacteria under light irradiation [25,27,146,147]. Central to this strategy is melanin's remarkable ability to convert absorbed light into heat, a process known as the photothermal effect. These photothermal effects arise from melanin's broad light absorption across the UV-visible spectrum, which is attributed to its heterogeneous polymeric structure and the resulting distribution of HOMO-LUMO band gaps. Upon photon absorption, excited electrons predominantly relax back to the ground state via nonradiative pathways, efficiently converting absorbed energy into localized heat. This localized heating can effectively disrupt bacterial membranes [18].

4.4. Antiviral properties

One pioneering study showed that synthetic melanin can inhibit the replication of HIV-1 and HIV-2 in human lymphoblastoid cell lines without causing toxicity [148]. It blocks the

HIV-1 envelope surface glycoprotein and the binding of the T cell-specific monoclonal antibody leu-3a (CD4) to cells, but does not interfere with the activity of the reverse transcriptase enzyme [148]. In another study, melanin extracted from *Inonotus obliquus* mushrooms cultured under electric light with the addition of 10 and 20 mM tyrosine exhibited the highest selectivity index against the HIV-1 retrovirus [31]. Melanin produced by black fungus demonstrated antiviral activity against HSV-1 through inhibiting plaque formation by 77%, indicating that HSV-1 is highly sensitive to this melanin [139]. Ink extracts from young cephalopods also strongly inhibited Moloney murine leukaemia virus reverse transcriptase (MMLV) [149]. Additionally, *in silico* studies show that melanin precursors (DHICA and L-DOPA) strongly interact with the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein, suggesting their potential use as antiviral compounds [150].

4.5. Photoprotective properties.

Melanin, a ubiquitous biological pigment found across a wide range of organisms, has long been recognized for its critical role in photoprotection. Its unique physicochemical properties enable it to absorb and dissipate harmful UV and ionizing radiation, thereby minimizing cellular and molecular damage. The protective capabilities of melanin are not limited to UV shielding; they extend to defense against high-energy radiation such as X-rays and gamma rays, making it a promising candidate for use in radiation protection strategies [90].

Seelam et al. demonstrated that natural melanin obtained from *Pseudomonas*-derived melanin exhibited a cell viability of $61.33 \pm 6.58\%$ at a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, proving its non-cytotoxic effect. Due to its antioxidant property (**Figure 2c**), melanin efficiently protected mouse fibroblast cells from UV-B irradiation in a dose-dependent manner, demonstrating its potential as an active photoprotective agent [140]. Moreover, pyomelanin produced by *A. niger* demonstrated strong antioxidant properties and provided significant protection against UV-C-induced stress [151]. Additionally, melanin extracted from cuttlefish ink has been investigated for its potential use as a photoprotective agent in hair-care formulations [70].

In addition to UV protection, melanin can also protect against ionizing radiation such as X-rays and gamma rays [14,16]. Melanized fungi have been found thriving on the walls of Chernobyl's damaged Reactor No. 4, where they survive and grow despite high radiation levels [152]. In a study by Dadachova et al., fungal melanin was shown to enhance the survival of human pathogenic fungi *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Histoplasma capsulatum* under high-dose gamma irradiation up to 8 kGy, with melanized cells exhibiting significantly greater

resistance than non-melanized cells [153]. Building on these findings, researchers have explored the potential of melanin-rich natural sources as practical radioprotective agents. Black edible mushrooms (*Auricularia auricula-judae*) served as effective oral radioprotectors in mice exposed to high-dose irradiation, providing 80% survival by reducing intestinal damage and restoring blood cell counts [154]. Eumelanin from the fungus *Gliocephalotrichum* was tested as a protective coating for seeds under gamma radiation. Melanin-coated dishes significantly improved seed germination and protected them from high-dose radiation, achieving nearly 100% survival, where unprotected seeds showed 50-60% mortality [155].

Beyond fungal systems, marine-derived melanin has also demonstrated radioprotective potential. Nguyen et al. demonstrated that squid ink melanin nanoparticles exhibit high biocompatibility, low cytotoxicity, and no cell senescence induction. In their study, X-ray irradiation significantly reduced the viability of human fibroblasts (hFBs) at various doses; however, the use of melanin nanoparticles effectively restored cell viability in hFBs, demonstrating a protective effect against the negative impacts of irradiation (**Figure 2d**) [15]. Similarly, Nguyen Thi et al. investigated melanin extracted from squid ink for its protective effects against X-ray irradiation in HaCaT keratinocyte cells. Treatment with nanomelanin increased cell viability by approximately 10% depending on the radiation dose and reduced the expression of pro-apoptotic genes (BAX, TNF- α , Caspase 3) two days post-irradiation at doses of 3-5 Gy [156].

The mechanisms underlying melanin-mediated radioprotection can be delineated as follows. First, melanin is capable of absorbing ionizing radiation and dissipating the absorbed energy as heat. Second, it serves as a biological shield by sequestering and neutralizing free radicals and ROS generated during the interaction of radiation with cellular macromolecules. Third, melanin possesses the ability to scatter radiation, altering its trajectory and consequently reducing the effective dose delivered to cellular targets [16,151,153].

5. Natural melanin in biomedical applications

5.1. Wound Healing

There is growing interest in novel biomaterials that can simultaneously alleviate oxidative stress, combat infection, and reduce inflammation during wound healing. Natural melanin has emerged as a promising candidate, since it provides multifunctional benefits when incorporated into wound dressings. For example, Qu et al. developed a system using cuttlefish ink nanoparticles (CINPs) functionalized with a zwitterionic polymer (CINP@ZP) to treat

multidrug-resistant wound infections (**Figure 3a**). These nanoparticles enabled deep wound penetration, provided effective photothermal killing of *S.aureus* and *E. coli*, and activated macrophage-mediated immune responses. Incorporated into a thermosensitive Pluronic F127 hydrogel for in situ spraying, CINP@ZP demonstrated significant antibacterial efficacy in infected mouse wound models [40].

In a complementary strategy, natural melanin nanoparticles extracted from human hair were incorporated into adhesive microparticles (AMPs) based on a chitosan oligosaccharide-polyacrylic acid (CSO-PAA) hydrogel matrix, prepared via microfluidic electrospray (**Figure 3b**). These melanin-loaded AMPs exhibited strong ROS-scavenging capacity, reducing oxidative stress at the wound site. Furthermore, under NIR irradiation, the embedded melanin nanoparticles promoted photothermal-enhanced tissue repair, highlighting the versatility of melanin across different wound healing modalities. By day 8, the AMPs+Melanin+NIR group exhibited the most advanced wound healing outcomes among all treatment groups [157].

Notably, the incorporation of melanin nanoparticles into hydrogels and nanofibers has emerged as an effective strategy for enhancing their functional performance. In a recent study, a konjac glucomannan/xanthan gum food biogel doped with cuttlefish ink melanin nanoparticles reduced full-thickness diabetic rat wounds to 7.1 ± 0.8 % of their initial area by day 15, whereas untreated defects still measured 26.0 ± 1.2 %. This rapid closure was confirmed to result from scavenging of ROS mediated by melanin nanoparticles derived from cuttlefish ink. The treatment lowered ROS fluorescence *in vivo*, suppressed TNF- α , and stimulated endothelial cell adhesion molecule-1 (CD31)-positive angiogenesis, along with dense collagen deposition and the formation of new hair follicles, ultimately restoring native skin architecture [158].

Xu et al., on the other hand, employed a tremella fuciformis polysaccharide hydrogel containing melanin nanoparticles derived from cuttlefish ink to treat *S. aureus*-infected diabetic wounds. Under NIR irradiation the treated wounds closed completely within 14 days, whereas saline-treated controls remained unhealed [146]. Similarly, Hao et al. developed a marine-inspired multifunctional hydrogel incorporating cuttlefish ink derived melanin nanoparticles for treating multidrug-resistant bacterial skin infections. The hydrogel demonstrated effective antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* upon NIR irradiation. By day 9 of *in vivo* testing, the remaining wound area in the PBS-treated group was 18%, whereas the group treated with the melanin nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel combined with NIR irradiation showed a significantly reduced wound area of only 4% [159].

Xiang et al. developed a light-activated hydrogel patch (SCE2) with cuttlefish ink nanoparticles for enhanced oral mucosal healing (**Figure 3c**). The hydrogel, made from methacrylate silk fibroin and nitrobenzyl-modified chondroitin sulfate, formed an adhesive barrier on mucosal injuries under UV light for prolonged site-specific retention. In diabetic rat models with oral ulcers, the SCE2 patch significantly enhanced re-epithelialization and angiogenesis while reducing local inflammation, demonstrating its potential as an effective bioactive platform for the management of oral mucosal injuries [39]. In the *S. aureus*-infected full-thickness back-skin model, SCE2 dressings shrank the wound area to 14.8 % after 14 days, and a single 3-min NIR pulse drove it down to just 8.1 %, whereas commercial 3M Tegaderm still left about 31% unhealed. In parallel, the same hydrogel closed chemically induced oral ulcers almost completely within five days under SCE2 + NIR, while PBS controls remained swollen and coated by a pseudomembrane [39]. Additionally, in the application for oral diabetic ulcer healing, Song et al. created an injectable polysaccharide hydrogel (OQC2) through dynamic Schiff-base cross-linking between oxidised dextran and quaternised chitosan, uniformly embedding cuttlefish-ink melanin nanoparticles that impart rapid self-gelation, broad antibiosis, and strong ROS-scavenging capacity (**Figure 3d**). In a streptozotocin-diabetic rat model bearing *S. aureus*-infected mucosal ulcers, a single OQC2 dose visibly contracted the lesions by day 3 and left them almost closed at day 7, outperforming PBS and nanoparticle-free controls [160].

While cuttlefish ink has been the predominant marine source, mussel shell waste is emerging as a promising yet underexplored alternative for melanin extraction. T-melanin extracted from mussel shells using acid hydrolysis and enzymolysis demonstrated effective eradication of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* under NIR irradiation, with *in vivo* results in rats confirming its wound healing potential [161]. Besides animal-derived sources, microbial melanin can be obtained from the Antarctic black, yeast-like fungus *Nadsoniella nigra* strain X1-M. A hydrogel composed of carbopol and melanin shortened rat excisional wound closure by approximately two days, accelerated chemical-burn healing, and demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* [162].

In the context of wound healing, Janahmadi et al. developed a haemostatic substance by incorporating melanin nanoparticles from cuttlefish ink into a cuttlebone biocomposite. By dramatically speeding up clot formation and demonstrating a rapid liquid absorption capacity, the resultant porous structure cut the whole blood clotting time to about 110 seconds from over 300 seconds for control samples. The melanin nanoparticles demonstrated over 95% inhibition against *S. aureus*, contributing to both hemostatic enhancement and antibacterial activity. *In*

in vivo testing in rat tail amputation and liver injury models confirmed effective bleeding control [163].

Figure 3. Wound healing application a) Preparation and application of a thermosensitive hydrogel loaded with zwitterion-functionalized cuttlefish ink nanoparticles (CIMP@ZP) for infected wound treatment. The system enables in situ gelation, photothermal antibacterial activity under NIR irradiation, and immune modulation to accelerate healing. Reproduced with permission [40], Copyright 2023 Elsevier B.V. b) Human hair-derived melanin nanoparticles integrated into adhesive microparticles (AMPs) for ROS scavenging and NIR-enhanced photothermal wound healing. Reproduced with permission [157], Copyright 2023, Elsevier Ltd., c) Top: Synthesis of the light-activated SCE2 hydrogel with cuttlefish ink nanoparticles. Bottom: Application of SCE2 in bacteria-infected diabetic rats, demonstrating reduced inflammation and enhanced re-epithelialization, angiogenesis, and tissue remodeling. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [39], Copyright 2024, The Authors. d) Top: Synthetic

route for preparing OQC2 hydrogel. Bottom: Proposed mechanisms by which OQC2 accelerates healing of oral mucosal wounds. Reproduced with permission [160], Copyright 2024 Elsevier B.V.

5.2. Tissue Regeneration

Recent research has increasingly highlighted the promise of natural melanin as a multifunctional component in tissue engineering scaffolds due to its inherent biocompatibility, antioxidant properties, and photothermal responsiveness. In the study by D'Amora et al., eumelanin extracted from the black soldier fly was incorporated into methacrylated hyaluronic acid to fabricate 3D-printed scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. The composite scaffolds demonstrated mechanical stability and supported the adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells [164]. Similarly, Huang et al. developed a 3D-printed hydrogel scaffold comprising gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA), nanohydroxyapatite, and melanin nanoparticles derived from cuttlefish ink, which gradually released melanin (~45% by day 21) (**Figure 4a**). This sustained release enabled efficient scavenging of ROS and promoted the polarization of infiltrating macrophages from the pro-inflammatory M0/M1 phenotype toward the regenerative M2 phenotype within the first week. The M2 macrophages secreted elevated levels of leukemia-inhibitory factor (Lif), and their conditioned medium significantly enhanced osteogenic differentiation of MC3T3 pre-osteoblasts *in vitro*. *In vivo*, the scaffold facilitated the repair of 2 mm cranial defects in mice, nearly doubling the bone volume per total volume ratio and supporting the formation of mature lamellar bone between weeks 4 and 8. [165].

In the study by Zhou et al., natural melanin nanoparticles from cuttlefish ink were incorporated into alginate hydrogels to create an injectable system (MNPs/Alg hydrogel) for myocardial infarction therapy (**Figure 4b**). The hydrogel targeted the damaged cardiac microenvironment by scavenging ROS species and promoting macrophage polarization to the regenerative M2 phenotype. *In vitro*, the hydrogel reduced oxidative stress, improved cardiomyocyte viability, enhanced cardiac protein expression, and promoted angiogenesis. *In vivo*, it decreased inflammation and apoptosis, increased vascular density, and supported myocardial regeneration. After 28 days in a rat model, treatment led to a reduced infarct size (from 54.3% to 20.7%), with a visibly smaller infarct area compared to the PBS and alginate hydrogel groups, as shown in **Figure 4b** on the right. It also resulted in thicker ventricular walls (from 0.42 mm to 1.23 mm) and significantly improved heart function. This approach achieved effective cardiac repair without using stem cells, drugs, or gene therapy [137].

Melanin sourced from yak hair was recently explored as an additive to polyurethane for developing shape-memory materials responsive to NIR light. Uniformly distributed melanin allowed for rapid NIR absorption, which raised the temperature by more than 40 °C in 60 seconds at 1.6 W/cm², which was enough to initiate shape recovery with a 97% recovery ratio. Additionally, the composite demonstrated strong mechanical qualities, such as exceptional repeatability over deformation cycles and a tensile strength of 18.9 MPa. Hair-derived melanin's long-term biocompatibility was confirmed by *in vivo* implantation in rats, which demonstrated minimal inflammation and negligible fibrous capsule formation after 28 days. This supported the use of hair-derived melanin as a sustainable, NIR-responsive filler for light-activated scaffolds in tissue engineering [67].

Figure 4. a) Top: Preparation of a 3D-printable bio-ink composed of gelatin, nano-hydroxyapatite, and cuttlefish-ink melanin, cross-linked with photo initiator (LAP) under 405 nm light to form a porous scaffold. Bottom: Application of the scaffold to a mouse calvarial defect reduces ROS and pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α), promotes M2 macrophage polarization (CD206⁺, Arg-1⁺), and enhances osteogenesis for accelerated bone regeneration. Reproduced with permission [165], Copyright 2025 Elsevier B.V. b) Top: Preparation of an injectable alginate hydrogel incorporating cuttlefish-ink-derived melanin nanoparticles (MNPs), cross-linked with Ca²⁺. Bottom: Following injection into rats with

myocardial infarction (MI), the hydrogel scavenges ROS, reduces cardiomyocyte apoptosis, promotes M2 macrophage polarization, and enhances angiogenesis, leading to improved cardiac repair. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [39,137], Copyright 2021, The Authors. c) Microfluidically fabricated melanin-integrated porous microparticles for NIR-responsive, controlled antibacterial therapy in periodontitis models, achieving targeted inhibition of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and reducing local inflammation. Reproduced with permission [27], Copyright 2023 Wiley-VCH GmbH. d) Demineralized mussel shell waste serving as a sustainable melanin platform for photothermal bacterial eradication on contact lenses under low-power light. Reproduced with permission [25], Copyright 2024 Wiley-VCH GmbH

5.3. Disinfection

As described in section 4.3, melanin derived from natural sources, including microorganisms, plants, and animals, exhibits significant antibacterial activity. Despite these promising properties, the range of tested biomedical applications remains relatively limited. As discussed in section 5.1, studies on wound healing have demonstrated that melanin not only promotes tissue regeneration but also reduces infection by inhibiting pathogens such as *S. aureus* and *E. Coli*. In addition to wound healing, melanin has been applied in diverse antibacterial contexts, including photothermal surface disinfection and targeted microbial eradication. In the study by Song et al., melanin derived from cuttlefish ink was incorporated into thermoresponsive porous microparticles fabricated via microfluidics for the treatment of periodontitis, demonstrating potent antibacterial activity under NIR irradiation (**Figure 4c**). These melanin nanoparticles were encapsulated in thermally responsive porous microparticles composed of poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) and agarose, enabling controlled release upon NIR stimulation. *In vitro* studies demonstrated a ~96% kill rate against *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, a key periodontopathogen. Notably, the system also showed broad-spectrum antibacterial effects, including against *S. aureus*, and exhibited excellent cytocompatibility. In a rat periodontal infection model, the application of melanin-loaded MPs with NIR irradiation promoted tissue regeneration and decreased local expression of inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-6 [27].

A recent study explored disinfection strategies for catheter-associated infections by demonstrating that natural melanin thin films derived from cuttlefish ink can rapidly inactivate bacteria through a photodynamic approach. Using layer-by-layer assembled melanin nanoparticle coatings, the study achieved 86.7% inactivation of *E. coli* and 80.5% of *S. aureus* after just 60 seconds of UV-A irradiation at a 1 cm distance. This method offers fast and

effective surface disinfection while avoiding the cytotoxicity associated with UV-C light and metal-based nanoparticles, making it a safe and promising strategy for antimicrobial medical device coatings [166].

Demonstrating a novel approach, Bartolewska et al. showed that demineralized mussel shells, which retain natural eumelanin in the periostracum layer, can serve as an effective, sustainable platform for the photothermal eradication of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* on contact lenses (**Figure 4d**). The nanoplatform exhibited efficient photothermal conversion under irradiation from a bike LED flashlight, reaching temperatures up to 95 °C at a distance of 3 cm with a power density of 320 mW/cm². The treatment maintained the water content and optical clarity of the lenses, and no cytotoxic effects were observed on L929 fibroblast cells. This portable and chemical-free disinfection method utilizes mussel shell-derived eumelanin as a novel photothermal material [25].

A study published recently by García-García et al. explored using biowaste from pecan nut shells [167]. In the context of food packaging, melanin extracted from these shells was incorporated into a polycaprolactone-gelatin solution and processed through electrospinning. The resulting material showed strong antioxidant and antifungal activity against *Fragaria x ananassa* L., due to the release of H₂O₂ during catechol oxidation [167]. Building on these findings, García-García et al. later tested the potential of pecan shell melanin in biomedical applications [168]. In this follow-up study, melanin was added to a polyacrylonitrile solution, and nanofibrous mats for skin-related uses were produced by electrospinning. These mats displayed antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus*. They also effectively inhibited skin-aging enzymes, including tyrosinase, hyaluronidase, elastase, and collagenase [168].

5.4. Cancer Therapy

PTT is a minimally invasive cancer treatment that uses light-responsive agents to selectively destroy tumor cells. Natural melanin, with its broad-spectrum light absorption, high photothermal conversion efficiency, and inherent biocompatibility, has emerged as a promising candidate for this approach. In the study by Guo et al., *E. coli* bacteria were engineered to produce natural melanin, combined with synthetic photosensitizers indocyanine green and PDA, forming a ternary system (**Figure 5a**). This combination strongly absorbed light at 808 nm, enhancing photoacoustic imaging and photothermal cancer therapy. In murine tumor models (4T1 breast and CT26 colon tumors), these bacteria effectively colonized hypoxic tumor areas, ensuring uniform distribution. Upon 808 nm laser irradiation (1.2 W/cm², 5

minutes), tumors reached around 60°C when using melanin with indocyanine green and PDA, significantly hotter than controls (melanin with PDA peaked at ~46°C, while melanin alone reached ~42°C). The treated tumors also produced photoacoustic signals about four times stronger than untreated ones, greatly improving imaging accuracy. Mice treated with a combination of melanin, PDA, and indocyanine green exhibited a marked reduction in tumor growth and a significant extension in survival, with lifespans exceeding 30 days compared to less than 23 days in the control group [169]. In a similar study, *Bacillus thuringiensis* was genetically engineered to biosynthesize natural melanin, enabling targeted tumor therapy (**Figure 5b**). The melanin-producing bacteria selectively accumulated in tumor tissues and, upon ultrasound and photothermal stimulation, generated ROS that enhanced therapeutic efficacy. *In vivo* experiments in mouse tumor models demonstrated approximately 90% tumor growth inhibition following NIR photothermal treatment, with no significant body weight loss [103]. As a natural photothermal agent, melanin has also been sourced from hair and incorporated into an injectable poloxamer sol-gel (Pol-Mel). In CT26 tumor-bearing mice, complete tumor ablation was achieved following a 3-minute exposure to NIR laser light (1.5 W/cm²) after Pol-Mel injection. In comparison, tumor volumes increased by 14.4 ± 4.9-fold in untreated controls, 7.6 ± 2.2-fold with Pol-Mel alone, and 5.4 ± 2.1-fold with laser alone [170].

To enhance photothermal therapy for skin cancer, microneedle patches provide a minimally invasive method to deliver photothermal agents directly to tumor sites. Lei et al. developed hyaluronic acid-based microneedle patches loaded with biomineralized melanin nanoparticles from cuttlefish ink, coated with silica (CINP@SiO₂), for combined photothermal treatment and wound healing (**Figure 5c**). The silica coating enabled the release of bioactive silicon ions to promote angiogenesis and skin regeneration. In mouse models, the patches penetrated subcutaneous tissue effectively, and under NIR irradiation (0.5 W/cm², 8 minutes), raised local temperatures to ~53°C, eliminating residual tumor cells without harming healthy tissue. The system also reduced *S. aureus* infection and enhanced endothelial cell migration, leading to 93% wound closure within 15 days, compared to 40-60% in controls [171].

In the study by Jia et al., a living photosynthetic microneedle patch (MA/CM@MN) was developed for postoperative melanoma therapy and wound healing. The patch combined microalgae (MA) in the base, which generated oxygen via photosynthesis, and cuttlefish melanin nanoparticles in the tips for photothermal therapy. Microneedles enabled painless, non-invasive delivery across the skin barrier. *In vitro*, the oxygen produced by MA alleviated hypoxia and supported cell proliferation. The melanin nanoparticles showed strong photothermal effects, effectively killing melanoma cells under NIR irradiation (808 nm, 0.50

W/cm²). *In vivo*, the patches heated tumor sites to ~55°C, reducing recurrence and accelerating wound healing. Immunofluorescence staining confirmed reduced proliferation, increased apoptosis, and improved oxygenation in the tumor microenvironment [172].

Figure 5. a) Top: Bioengineered bacteria expressing melanin are coated with dopamine and loaded with photosensitizers. Bottom: 808 nm laser irradiation enables photoacoustic imaging-guided photothermal therapy, leading to tumor lysis. Reproduced with permission [169], Copyright 2023 American Chemical Society. b) Genetically modified *Bacillus thuringiensis* oxidizes tyrosine into pyromelanin; the pigment’s NIR-activated photothermal effect both eradicates tumors and suppresses inflammatory signaling. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [103], 2024 The Authors c) Top: Extraction and modification of cuttlefish ink with biomimetic silicification. Bottom: Schematic of the therapeutic process using biomineralized melanin nanoparticle-loaded microneedle patches for subcutaneous melanoma postoperative wound healing. Reproduced with permission [171], Copyright 2022 Wiley-VCH GmbH. d) Preparation of living photosynthetic microneedle patches and their use in localized oxygen delivery and post-surgical melanoma treatment. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [172], Copyright 2024, The Authors.

5.5. Imaging and theranostics

Developing compact and biocompatible nanoplatforms that support multiple imaging modalities remains a major challenge. Imaging-guided therapy, which combines diagnosis and treatment in a single system, depends on such platforms to monitor drug delivery and treatment response in real time. In cancer therapy, these systems are designed to accurately visualize tumors and deliver therapeutic agents such as chemotherapy drugs or photothermal compounds. For this purpose, a variety of nanomaterials have been studied, such as silica nanoparticles, metal particles, carbon materials, and calcium-based systems. However, their clinical application is often limited due to concerns about long-term toxicity. Natural melanin has garnered increasing attention lately as a safer and multifunctional alternative [5].

Fu et al. reported melanin nanoparticles synthesized using *E. coli* genetically engineered to express tyrosinase, enabling biosynthesis under mild and scalable conditions (**Figure 6a**). The resulting nanoparticles were uniform, highly water-dispersible, and exhibited NIR absorption with a photothermal conversion efficiency of 48.9% under NIR laser irradiation, showing improved performance compared to PDA. These melanin nanoparticles were applied for PAI and PTT in tumor-bearing mice. *In vivo*, they accumulated efficiently in tumor tissues via passive targeting and produced strong photoacoustic signals for imaging [42].

In the study by Dong et al., melanin extracted from cuttlefish ink was used to develop a dual-mode imaging nanoprobe for lymphatic system mapping (**Figure 6b**). The melanin was PEGylated and conjugated with NIR-II fluorescent dye (H2), forming inkMNP-PEG-H2 nanoparticles. These particles exhibited excellent water solubility, biocompatibility, and strong NIR-II fluorescence, enabling high-resolution, real-time sentinel lymph node (SLN) imaging in tumor-bearing mice. The probe demonstrated rapid lymphatic uptake and prolonged retention. To enable preoperative imaging, the melanin nanoparticles were also chelated with Gd^{3+} ions to form inkMNP-PEG-Gd, allowing effective MRI-based detection of metastatic lymph nodes. Additionally, the natural brown-black color of melanin enabled naked-eye intraoperative identification of SLNs [173]. Similarly, Chu et al. extracted melanin from black sesame seeds to develop liposome-coated melanin nanoparticles (liposome-BSM). Due to their intrinsic pigmentation and strong NIR absorption, these nanoparticles were used for both SLN mapping and PTT. The particles enabled visual tracking of lymph nodes and, upon NIR laser irradiation, induced significant tumor cell damage [174].

Using melanin-loaded nanodroplets, researchers achieved combined imaging and therapy by co-encapsulating cuttlefish ink melanin nanoparticles and doxorubicin (DOX) within perfluoropentane nanodroplets. Upon opto-acoustic activation, the droplets vaporized

into microbubbles, enhancing ultrasound and photoacoustic imaging while improving DOX penetration [175]. Meanwhile, Wang et al. fabricated cuttlefish melanin nanospheres decorated *in situ* with gold nanoparticles by exploiting melanin's intrinsic reductive chemistry in a single, room-temperature step. Intratumoral administration in 4T1 breast tumor-bearing mice yields high-contrast computed tomography, PAI, and infrared thermal imaging that clearly delineate tumor margins [41].

In the study by Fan et al., melanin nanoparticles were prepared by dissolving synthetic melanin granules derived from cultured cells in alkaline solution, followed by ultrasonic treatment to form ultrasmall (<10 nm), water-soluble particles. These nanoparticles exhibited strong broadband optical absorption and high affinity for metal ions, enabling their use in multimodal imaging, including PAI, positron emission tomography (PET) through ^{64}Cu labeling, and MRI via Fe^{3+} chelation. Additionally, conjugation with cyclic RGD peptides, which specifically bind to $\alpha\text{v}\beta 3$ integrins overexpressed in tumor vasculature, enabled active targeting of the nanoparticles to tumor sites. This significantly enhanced imaging contrast and demonstrated the potential of the system for precise, receptor-mediated tumor localization and monitoring *in vivo* [4].

Figure 6. a) Top: Biosynthesis of melanin nanoparticles using engineered *E. coli*. Bottom: Photoacoustic imaging-guided photothermal therapy for cancer treatment using biosynthetic melanin nanoparticles. Reproduced with permission [42], Copyrights 2022 Wiley-VCH GmbH. b) Top: Preparation of dual-mode imaging probes based on cuttlefish-derived melanin nanoparticles (inkMNPs), modified with PEG and either the NIR-II fluorescent dye H2 (inkMNP-PEG-H2) or gadolinium ions (inkMNP-PEG-Gd). Bottom: InkMNP-PEG-H2 enables high-contrast, long-lasting mapping of sentinel lymph nodes (SLNs) through NIR-II fluorescence and naked-eye detection, while inkMNP-PEG-Gd supports preoperative SLN evaluation via MRI. Reproduced with permission [173], Copyrights 2022 Elsevier Inc. c) Multimodal molecular imaging using melanin nanoparticles (MNPs) derived from melanocyte cells. Melanin granules were dissolved in 0.1 M NaOH and neutralized under sonication to obtain uniform, water-dispersible nanoparticles. The MNPs were surface-modified with PEG and functionalized with RGD peptides for tumor targeting. Chelation with Fe^{3+} and ^{64}Cu enabled photoacoustic (PAI), magnetic resonance (MRI), and positron emission tomography (PET) imaging. Reproduced with permission [4], Copyrights 2014 American Chemical Society.

5.6. Drug Delivery Systems

Melanin's unique structure and surface properties enable it to bind small-molecule drugs effectively, making it a promising natural carrier for controlled and targeted drug delivery. *In silico* studies by Soltani et al. showed that drug-eumelanin binding depends on molecular charge, conformation, and π - π interactions. Charged chloroquine and methotrexate exhibited strong binding, highlighting melanin's potential for drug delivery applications [176]. Natural melanin nanoparticles from *Sepia officinalis* have been used as a drug delivery platform for osteosarcoma, achieving 99% DOX loading efficiency and strong photothermal effects under NIR light. This system enabled controlled drug release and reduced cancer cell viability by 93% within 48 hours, demonstrating effective, low-toxicity chemo-photothermal therapy [177]. The same research group previously demonstrated the use of functionalized melanin nanoparticles, coated with PDA and polypyrrole, for electrically triggered delivery of dexamethasone. The optimized nanoparticles achieved a drug loading efficiency of 94.5%. Under passive conditions, dexamethasone release remained below 10% after 24 hours, whereas electrical stimulation increased the release to approximately 32% [178]. Besides cuttlefish ink melanin, Gao et al. reported the use of melanin extracted from apricot kernels to fabricate PEGylated melanin nanoparticles for pH-responsive drug delivery applications. The

nanoparticles exhibited high DOX loading efficiency and enabled pH-dependent release, with approximately 40.8% of DOX released at pH 5.0 compared to 11.9% at pH 7.4 over 24 hours [179]. Additionally, Zhang et al. proposed an innovative approach using nanoparticles derived from beard hair of young males, composed mainly of keratin and melanin with strong photothermal properties. The negatively charged surfaces enabled efficient adsorption of positively charged fluoxetine. The drug loading content was 46.7%, and under NIR irradiation, approximately 80% of fluoxetine was released within 70 minutes. Moreover, less than 12% leakage was observed over 7 days at 4 °C, indicating good stability. This system facilitated fluoxetine transport across the blood-brain barrier and provided antioxidant protection, offering a promising strategy to enhance antidepressant delivery and therapeutic efficacy [65].

5.7. Supplementation

Oral delivery of melanin offers a novel approach to harness its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and protective properties. Xiao et al. recently demonstrated the efficacy of orally administered natural melanin nanozymes (NMNs) isolated from octopus ink sacs in addressing systemic aging-associated pathologies (**Figure 7a**). Robust superoxide dismutase-mimetic and radical scavenging activities were observed, resulting in significant mitigation of oxidative stress and neuroinflammation *in vivo*. In an aged senescence-accelerated mouse prone 8 (SAMP8) mouse strain, NMN supplementation improved cognitive performance, memory retention, and hepatic metabolic profiles while modulating gut microbiota composition by increasing microbial diversity, collectively contributing to lifespan extension [180].

Similarly, Xie et al. demonstrated that orally administered melanin extracted from *Sepia pharaonis* ink (MSI) alleviated ulcerative colitis in mice induced by dextran sulfate sodium (DSS) by reducing inflammation and oxidative stress, preserving the intestinal barrier, and restoring gut microbiota balance [20]. Building on this work, the same research group further evaluated the multifunctional potential of orally administered melanin (75-300 mg/kg/day) in a DSS-induced colitis model. In this follow-up study, intestinal inflammation was effectively mitigated, while depression- and anxiety-like behaviors were reversed, emphasizing the gut-brain axis as a key target of melanin's systemic activity [181]. In a subsequent investigation, Xie et al. explored the therapeutic potential of MSI in an ethanol-induced gastric ulcer model (**Figure 7b**). Oral administration of MSI significantly reduced ulcer area and gastric bleeding, while enhancing antioxidant defenses and preserving mucosal integrity. The protective effects were associated with reduced inflammation, modulation of TLR4/MAPK signaling pathway, and suppression of epithelial apoptosis [138].

In another example, Hou et al. investigated the therapeutic potential of melanin extracted from the edible fungus *Auricularia auricula*. Oral administration of this fungal melanin significantly alleviated alcohol-induced liver damage in mice. It worked by improving antioxidant enzyme activity (SOD, CAT), lowering lipid peroxidation markers, suppressing the expression of CYP2E1 (a major oxidative stress inducer), and activating the Nrf2 signaling pathway, which led to increased expression of detoxifying and antioxidant genes. The treatment also improved liver function markers and restored hepatic tissue integrity, reinforcing its role as a hepatoprotective agent [182].

Figure 7. a) Orally administered natural melanin nanozymes from octopus ink demonstrates systemic anti-aging effects through antioxidant activity and modulation of gut microbiota in aged mice. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [180], Copyright 2025, The Authors. b) Oral administration of melanin from *Sepiapharaonis* alleviated alcohol-induced gastric ulcers in rats. The treatment reduced the ulcer index, suppressed inflammation, inhibited cell apoptosis via caspase-3 modulation, and regulated EGFR and TLR4/MAPK signaling pathways. Reproduced with permission [138], Copyright 2022 Elsevier Ltd. c) Hair-derived melanin particles with non-penetrative morphology applied in sunscreen formulations, offering UV protection while serving as mesoporous drug carriers. Reproduced with permission [33],

Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society. d) Melanin extracted from *Amorphotheca resinae* demonstrates UV protection in broad-spectrum sunscreen and antioxidant activity. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license [32], Copyright 2021, The Authors.

5.8. Sunscreen / Photoprotection

Prolonged exposure to UV radiation can cause harmful effects on human skin, including sunburn, premature aging, and skin cancers [183]. Skin pigmentation, which involves melanin production, serves as a crucial photoprotective measure in animals and humans. Melanin helps protect skin cells, especially keratinocytes, from UV-induced genetic damage by absorbing harmful rays and neutralizing ROS [184–186]. While these natural defense mechanisms offer some protection, excessive sunlight exposure can still damage skin. To address this issue, modern skincare solutions have integrated sunscreens as an external method of protection against UV radiation. Although traditional sunscreens can reduce skin damage to some extent, concerns about the safety of conventional UV filters are growing. Among the various approaches, sunscreens that mimic melanin are becoming increasingly popular due to their advantageous properties, such as high biocompatibility, minimal skin penetration, strong antioxidant capabilities, and the ability to absorb both UVA and UVB spectra [140,187–189].

To address this, natural particles derived from human hair (HDPs) have been developed as a multifunctional sunscreen (**Figure 7c**). Their mesoporous, fusiform structure enables drug loading while preventing deep skin penetration, enhancing safety. *In vivo* studies on UV-irradiated mice showed that HDPs significantly reduced epidermal thickening (−77.8%), and HDPs loaded with octocrylene (Oct@HDPs) completely prevented skin hyperplasia, maintaining normal skin structure. *In vitro* tests confirmed their low cytotoxicity and ability to suppress UV-induced ROS production in 3T3 cells, unlike commercial sunscreens, TiO₂, or free UV filters, which showed higher toxicity and oxidative stress. These results highlight HDPs and Oct@HDPs as safe and effective natural materials for UV protection [33].

Oh et al. evaluated melanin from fungi *Amorphotheca resinae* for sunscreen performance, antioxidant activity, and cytotoxicity. A melanin-blended cream showed an *in vitro* SPF (sun protection factor) of 2.5 at 5% pigment content, with a critical wavelength of 388 nm and a UVA/UVB ratio of 0.81, meeting broad-spectrum sunscreen requirements (**Figure 7d**). The melanin exhibited antioxidant activity comparable to that of ascorbic acid and higher than that of reduced glutathione. Additionally, fungal melanin showed no statistically significant cytotoxicity to human keratinocyte cell lines during up to 72 hours of exposure [32].

Geng et al. investigated the photoprotective effects of melanin derived from the bacteria *Pseudomonas maltophilia* against UVA radiation. Using human fibroblasts, including cells from patients with xeroderma pigmentosum (XP), the researchers showed that bacterial melanin reduced ROS formation and increased cell viability after UVA exposure. Treated XP cells were more resistant to UVA-induced apoptosis than untreated XP or even normal fibroblasts. Importantly, in human skin tests, persistent pigment darkening was reduced by over 50% following topical application of bacterial melanin at concentrations up to 1000 µg/mL, while UVA transmission was decreased by only ~20%. This difference was interpreted as evidence that the photoprotective efficacy of bacterial melanin is not solely attributable to UV filtering, but is also mediated by biological antioxidant mechanisms [190].

Natural melanin has already been commercialized by a French company called The Innovation Company. It has launched two additives for sun care and skin care: Creanatural® Sepia Melanin, containing melanin derived from squid ink [191], and Creanatural® Vegetable Melanin, with melanin extracted from date fruits [192], both serving as antioxidants and UV filters. Moreover, a Polish brand called Health Labs Care includes natural melanin derived from fungi in its Glow On SPF 50+ cream as an antioxidant and photoprotection booster [193].

6. Conclusion and outlook

Natural melanin in the form of a multifunctional biopigment is a promising candidate for complex biomedical applications due to its inherent physicochemical properties, biocompatibility, and diverse bioactivities. Its unique property to absorb the ultraviolet (UV) and near-infrared (NIR) spectral bands, along with its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and photothermal activities, makes melanin an efficient agent in modern therapeutic strategies involving wound healing, photothermal therapy for cancers, antimicrobial therapy, and radioprotection. Furthermore, the ability of melanin to modulate oxidative stress and inflammatory processes and its metal-chelating properties indicate its application in treating neurodegenerative disorders and in the development of protectant biomedical devices.

Application of sustainable, natural sources of melanin from animals, plants, fungi, and bacteria maintains a circular bioeconomy while keeping medical applications scalable without compromising environmental integrity. Advances in extraction and formulation procedures, most notably environment-friendly and green extraction procedures, have also allowed the

encapsulation of melanin in hydrogels, microneedles, and nanoformulations to widen its application across drug delivery and regenerative medicine.

Despite its promise, translating melanin into practical medical and technological applications remains challenging [194]. One significant barrier is the difficulty of isolating natural melanin from complex biological matrices such as skin, hair, or fungal cell walls. Extraction methods - such as hydrochloric acid hydrolysis for eumelanin (from cuttlefish ink or human hair), or harsh alkaline treatments for fungal melanin - can degrade essential structural components like DHICA units and lead to significant loss of antioxidant functionality, especially at higher acid concentrations [195]. Pheomelanin, abundant in red hair, is particularly scarce and chemically unstable, further limiting its utility. Microbial systems (e.g. *Streptomyces glaucescens*, *A. niger*) offer scalable production routes but suffer from low yields and genetic instability [127]. Additionally, even when extraction yields are high, the resulting material may be of low purity. Because melanins are often tightly associated with cellular components, isolating pure melanin is challenging [105]. Meanwhile, synthetic analogs such as PDA provide reliable production and tunable surface chemistry, and are generally described as biocompatible in a variety of regenerative medicine applications [196,197]. An additional challenge lies in the nomenclature of melanin pigments. Several studies describe pigments as melanin-like even when extracted from natural sources, as such pigments frequently display properties resembling melanin but remain challenging to confirm and unambiguously identify [198–200]. This lack of clear classification blurs the distinction between natural melanins and related polyphenolic compounds.

Melanin's intrinsic structural heterogeneity complicates both synthesis and characterization. Unlike well-defined synthetic polymers, natural melanin lacks a consistent molecular architecture, posing challenges for reproducibility, quality control, and regulatory approval in medical applications [201]. To address this, advanced spectroscopic techniques and computational modeling are critical for elucidating structure-property-function relationships.

Recent innovations aim to overcome extraction and scalability barriers through sustainable production methods, including microbial fermentation and plant-based extraction [45]. For instance, *B. subtilis* produces melanin with inherent antimicrobial properties, while edible fungi such as *Auricularia auricula* yield melanin with enhanced solubility and semiconductor properties, beneficial for edible bioelectronic applications [202,203]. Agricultural waste streams like grape pomace, rice husks, molasses, and spent coffee grounds also present cost-effective and environmentally friendly feedstocks, supporting circular bioeconomy goals [204]. However, standardized protocols are urgently needed to ensure

reproducibility and material quality. AI-driven process control, particularly in fermentation, has shown potential to increase yields by up to 50% by optimizing key parameters such as pH and temperature [205].

Melanin nanoparticles are emerging as multifunctional agents for next-generation medical devices. Their natural biocompatibility and capacity for drug loading via π - π stacking interactions enable combined PTT and chemotherapy, with reported photothermal conversion efficiencies of up to 40% under NIR irradiation [206]. MNPs can also be engineered to respond to acidic tumor microenvironments, enhancing their retention in the tumor and their contrast in PET imaging. Furthermore, MNPs are being explored for use in PAI, MRI, and multi-modal diagnostic platforms [5]. However, challenges remain in achieving uniform particle size, scalable synthesis, and clinical-grade purity. Compared to PDA, natural melanin often shows lower cytotoxicity in human cell lines and faster *in vivo* degradation, highlighting its potential for safer, nanomedicine [196]. However, PDA's surface functionalization capacity still offers advantages for targeted delivery and controlled drug release.

To conclude, melanin-based nanotechnology is promising for advancing precision medicine, reducing healthcare costs, and enabling sustainable material innovation. However, significant hurdles remain, including extraction inefficiencies, molecular heterogeneity, and clinical translation bottlenecks. Addressing these challenges will require a multidisciplinary approach integrating green chemistry, nanotechnology, synthetic biology, and computational modeling. Future research should prioritize standardized production from renewable sources, mechanistic studies on melanin's interactions with biological systems, scalable synthesis of uniform and functionalized MNPs, and rigorous regulatory and clinical validation to ensure safety and efficacy. Successfully addressing these challenges could position melanin nanomaterials as sustainable, cost-effective, and clinically impactful nanomedicine.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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References

- [1] Riley P A 1997 Melanin. *Int. J. Biochem. Cell Biol.* **29** 1235–9
- [2] Berg S Z and Berg J 2023 Melanin: a unifying theory of disease as exemplified by Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, and Lewy body dementia. *Front. Immunol.* **14** 1228530
- [3] Koike S and Yamasaki K 2020 Melanogenesis Connection with Innate Immunity and Toll-Like Receptors. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **21**
- [4] Fan Q, Cheng K, Hu X, Ma X, Zhang R, Yang M, Lu X, Xing L, Huang W, Gambhir S S and Cheng Z 2014 Transferring biomarker into molecular probe: melanin nanoparticle as a naturally active platform for multimodality imaging. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **136** 15185–94
- [5] Sun J, Han Y, Dong J, Lv S and Zhang R 2023 Melanin/melanin-like nanoparticles: As a naturally active platform for imaging-guided disease therapy. *Mater. Today Bio* **23** 100894
- [6] Yoo H-S, Chung K-H, Lee K-J, Kim D-H and An J H 2017 Melanin extract from *Gallus gallus domesticus* promotes proliferation and differentiation of osteoblastic MG-63 cells via bone morphogenetic protein-2 signaling. *Nutr. Res. Pract.* **11** 190–7
- [7] Qin Y and Xia Y 2024 Melanin in fungi: advances in structure, biosynthesis, regulation, and metabolic engineering. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **23** 334
- [8] Cao W, Zhou X, McCallum N C, Hu Z, Ni Q Z, Kapoor U, Heil C M, Cay K S, Zand T, Mantanona A J, Jayaraman A, Dhinojwala A, Deheyn D D, Shawkey M D, Burkart M D, Rinehart J D and Gianneschi N C 2021 Unraveling the Structure and Function of Melanin through Synthesis. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **143** 2622–37
- [9] Song W, Yang H, Liu S, Yu H, Li D, Li P and Xing R 2023 Melanin: insights into structure, analysis, and biological activities for future development. *J. Mater. Chem. B Mater. Biol. Med.* **11** 7528–43
- [10] Kim E, Wang Z, Phua J W, Bentley W E, Dadachova E, Napolitano A and Payne G F 2024 Enlisting electrochemistry to reveal melanin's redox-related properties *Mater. Adv.* **5** 3082–93
- [11] Gouda A, Masson A, Hoseinizadeh M, Soavi F and Santato C 2022 Biosourced quinones for high-performance environmentally benign electrochemical capacitors via interface engineering *Commun. Chem.* **5** 98
- [12] Motovilov K A, Grinenko V, Savinov M, Gagkaeva Z V, Kadyrov L S, Pronin A A, Bedran Z V, Zhukova E S, Mostert A B and Gorshunov B P 2019 Redox chemistry in the pigment

- eumelanin as a function of temperature using broadband dielectric spectroscopy *RSC Adv.* **9** 3857–67
- [13] Dai K, Cao S, Yuan J, Wang Z, Li H, Yuan C, Yan X and Xing R 2025 Recent advances of sustainable UV shielding materials: mechanisms and applications. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **17** 30402–22
- [14] Liu R, Meng X, Mo C, Wei X and Ma A 2022 Melanin of fungi: from classification to application. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **38** 228
- [15] Nguyen L-N T, Do X-H, Pham H B, Duy-Thanh D, Than U T T, Nguyen T-H, Nguyen V-B, Le D-S, Nguyen D-T, Kieu K T, Nguyen P T, Vu M D, Tran N T, Nguyen T L, Nghiem L T H, Nguyen T D, Nguyen N T H and Hoang N-T M 2024 Different biocompatibility and radioprotective activity of squid melanin nanoparticles on human stromal cells. *ACS Omega* **9** 36926–38
- [16] Cordero R J and Casadevall A 2017 Functions of fungal melanin beyond virulence. *Fungal Biol. Rev.* **31** 99–112
- [17] Malo M E, Frank C and Dadachova E 2019 Assessing melanin capabilities in radiation shielding and radioadaptation *J. Med. Imaging Radiat. Sci.* **50** S2
- [18] Xie W, Dhinojwala A, Gianneschi N C and Shawkey M D 2024 Interactions of Melanin with Electromagnetic Radiation: From Fundamentals to Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **124** 7165–213
- [19] Meredith P and Sarna T 2006 The physical and chemical properties of eumelanin. *Pigment Cell Res.* **19** 572–94
- [20] Xie J, Liu L, Li H, Che H and Xie W 2022 Ink melanin from *Sepiapharaonis* ameliorates colitis in mice via reducing oxidative stress, and protecting the intestinal mucosal barrier. *Food Res. Int.* **151** 110888
- [21] El-Obeid A, Maashi Y, AlRoshody R, Alatar G, Aljudayi M, Al-Eidi H, AlGaith N, Khan A H, Hassib A and Matou-Nasri S 2023 Herbal melanin modulates PGE2 and IL-6 gastroprotective markers through COX-2 and TLR4 signaling in the gastric cancer cell line AGS. *BMC Complement. Med. Ther.* **23** 305
- [22] Kurian N K, Nair H P and Bhat S G 2015 Evaluation of Anti-Inflammatory Property of Melanin from Marine *Bacillus* Sp BTCZ31 *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research* **8** 251–5
- [23] Yang X, Tang C, Zhao Q, Jia Y, Qin Y and Zhang J 2023 Melanin: A promising source of functional food ingredient *J. Funct. Foods* **105** 105574
- [24] Song S, Li S, Su N, Li J, Shi F and Ye M 2016 Structural characterization, molecular modification and hepatoprotective effect of melanin from *Lachnum* YM226 on acute alcohol-induced liver injury in mice. *Food Funct.* **7** 3617–27
- [25] Bartolewska M, Kosik-Kozioł A, Korwek Z, Krysiak Z, Montroni D, Mazur M, Falini G and Pierini F 2024 Eumelanin-Enhanced Photothermal Disinfection of Contact Lenses Using a Sustainable Marine Nanoplatfrom Engineered with Electrospun Nanofibers. *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* e2402431
- [26] Shu R, Liang Y, Liu S, Dou L, Bu T, Wang S, Lan X, Zhang D, Sun J, Zhu M and Wang J 2023 “From food waste to food supervision”-Cuttlefish Ink Natural Nanoparticles-Driven Dual-mode Lateral Flow Immunoassay for Advancing Point-of-Care Tests. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* **219** 114807

- [27] Song C, Wu X, Wang Y, Wang J and Zhao Y 2024 Cuttlefish-Inspired Photo-Responsive Antibacterial Microparticles with Natural Melanin Nanoparticles Spray. *Small* **20** e2310444
- [28] Rahmani Eliato T, Smith J T, Tian Z, Kim E-S, Hwang W, Andam C P and Kim Y J 2021 Melanin pigments extracted from horsehair as antibacterial agents. *J. Mater. Chem. B Mater. Biol. Med.* **9** 1536–45
- [29] Elsayis A, Hassan S W M, Ghanem K M and Khairy H 2022 Suggested Sustainable Medical and Environmental Uses of Melanin Pigment From Halotolerant Black Yeast *Hortaea werneckii* AS1. *Front. Microbiol.* **13** 871394
- [30] Minasyan E, Aghajanyan A, Karapetyan K, Khachaturyan N, Hovhannisyan G, Yeghyan K and Tsaturyan A 2024 Antimicrobial Activity of Melanin Isolated from Wine Waste. *Indian J. Microbiol.* **64** 1528–34
- [31] Teplyakova T V, Markovich N A, Gashnikova N M and Gashnikova M P 2023 Melanin Production by the Medicinal Mushroom *Inonotus obliquus* F-1375 in Submerged Liquid Cultivation and its Antiretroviral Properties *Appl. Biochem. Microbiol.* **59** 482–8
- [32] Oh J-J, Kim J Y, Son S H, Jung W-J, Kim D H, Seo J-W and Kim G-H 2021 Fungal melanin as a biocompatible broad-spectrum sunscreen with high antioxidant activity. *RSC Adv.* **11** 19682–9
- [33] Hong S, Peng Z, Wu M, Nie Y, Yi Y, Cai H and Zhang X-Z 2023 Human-Hair-Derived Natural Particles as Multifunctional Sunscreen for Effective UV Protection. *ACS Nano* **17** 14943–53
- [34] Motlagh-Haghnegahdar M, Mozafari N, Sobhani Z, Koohi-Hosseiniabadi O, Dehghanian A R, Tanideh N and Azadi A 2025 Natural-based melanin nanoparticles for simultaneous chemo/photothermal therapy of melanoma. *J. Pharm. Sci.* **114** 103850
- [35] Deng R-H, Zou M-Z, Zheng D, Peng S-Y, Liu W, Bai X-F, Chen H-S, Sun Y, Zhou P-H and Zhang X-Z 2019 Nanoparticles from Cuttlefish Ink Inhibit Tumor Growth by Synergizing Immunotherapy and Photothermal Therapy. *ACS Nano* **13** 8618–29
- [36] Li Y, Huang L, Li X, Geng P, Xiang J, Wang W, Yang B, Zheng Y, Lan H and Xiao S 2024 From biomaterials to biotherapy: cuttlefish ink with protoporphyrin IX nanoconjugates for synergistic sonodynamic-photothermal therapy. *J. Mater. Chem. B Mater. Biol. Med.* **12** 1837–45
- [37] Danielyan M, Nebogova K, Simonyan R, Hovsepian A, Avetisyan Z, Simonyan K, Simonyan G, Khachatryan V and Karapetyan K 2023 Regulatory effect of bacterial melanin on the isoforms of new superoxide-producing associates from rat tissues in rotenone-induced Parkinson's disease. *BMC Neurosci.* **24** 69
- [38] Petrosyan T 2015 Bacterial melanin in rat models of Parkinson's disease: a potential neuroprotective strategy. *Neural Regen. Res.* **10** 211–2
- [39] Xiang Y, Pan Z, Qi X, Ge X, Xiang J, Xu H, Cai E, Lan Y, Chen X, Li Y, Shi Y, Shen J and Liu J 2024 A cuttlefish ink nanoparticle-reinforced biopolymer hydrogel with robust adhesive and immunomodulatory features for treating oral ulcers in diabetes. *Bioact. Mater.* **39** 562–81
- [40] Qu W-Q, Fan J-X, Zheng D-W, Gu H-Y, Yu Y-F, Yan X, Zhao K, Hu Z-B, Qi B-W, Zhang X-Z and Yu A-X 2023 Deep-penetration functionalized cuttlefish ink nanoparticles for combating wound infections with synergetic photothermal-immunologic therapy. *Biomaterials* **301** 122231

- [41] Wang Z, Yu N, Yu W, Xu H, Li X, Li M, Peng C, Wang Q, Zhu M and Chen Z 2019 In situ growth of Au nanoparticles on natural melanin as biocompatible and multifunctional nanoagent for efficient tumor theranostics. *J. Mater. Chem. B Mater. Biol. Med.* **7** 133–42
- [42] Fu M, Yang Y, Zhang Z, He Y, Wang Y, Liu C, Xu X, Lin J and Yan F 2023 Biosynthesis of melanin nanoparticles for photoacoustic imaging guided photothermal therapy. *Small* **19** e2205343
- [43] Park J, Moon H and Hong S 2019 Recent advances in melanin-like nanomaterials in biomedical applications: a mini review. *Biomater. Res.* **23** 24
- [44] Caldas M, Santos A C, Veiga F, Rebelo R, Reis R L and Correlo V M 2020 Melanin nanoparticles as a promising tool for biomedical applications - a review. *Acta Biomater.* **105** 26–43
- [45] El-Naggar N E-A and Saber W I A 2022 Natural Melanin: Current Trends, and Future Approaches, with Especial Reference to Microbial Source. *Polymers (Basel)* **14**
- [46] Xie W, Pakdel E, Liang Y, Kim Y J, Liu D, Sun L and Wang X 2019 Natural eumelanin and its derivatives as multifunctional materials for bioinspired applications: A review. *Biomacromolecules* **20** 4312–31
- [47] Solano F 2014 Melanins: skin pigments and much more?types, structural models, biological functions, and formation routes *New J. Sci.* **2014** 1–28
- [48] Omucheni D L, Kaduki K A and Mukabana W R 2023 Identification of three medically important mosquito species using Raman spectroscopy *J. Raman Spectrosc.* **54** 512–23
- [49] Galván I, Jorge A, Edelaar P and Wakamatsu K 2015 Insects synthesize pheomelanin. *Pigment Cell Melanoma Res.* **28** 599–602
- [50] Cao W, Mao H, McCallum N C, Zhou X, Sun H, Sharpe C, Korpanty J, Hu Z, Ni Q Z, Burkart M D, Shawkey M D, Wasielewski M R and Gianneschi N C 2023 Biomimetic pheomelanin to unravel the electronic, molecular and supramolecular structure of the natural product. *Chem. Sci.* **14** 4183–92
- [51] Guo L, Li W, Gu Z, Wang L, Guo L, Ma S, Li C, Sun J, Han B and Chang J 2023 Recent advances and progress on melanin: from source to application. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **24**
- [52] Singh I K, Espinosa M L, Lim H W and Mohammad T F 2024 A review of therapies for hyperpigmentation modulating the synthesis of eumelanin to pheomelanin. *Arch. Dermatol. Res.* **316** 668
- [53] Zucca F A, Capucciati A, Bellei C, Sarna M, Sarna T, Monzani E, Casella L and Zecca L 2023 Neuromelanins in brain aging and Parkinson’s disease: synthesis, structure, neuroinflammatory, and neurodegenerative role. *IUBMB Life* **75** 55–65
- [54] Wakamatsu K, Tabuchi K, Ojika M, Zucca F A, Zecca L and Ito S 2015 Norepinephrine and its metabolites are involved in the synthesis of neuromelanin derived from the locus coeruleus. *J. Neurochem.* **135** 768–76
- [55] Krainc T, Monje M H G, Kinsinger M, Bustos B I and Lubbe S J 2023 Melanin and neuromelanin: linking skin pigmentation and parkinson’s disease. *Mov. Disord.* **38** 185–95
- [56] Filimontseva A, Fu Y, Vila M and Halliday G M 2025 Neuromelanin and selective neuronal vulnerability to Parkinson’s disease. *Trends Neurosci.* **48** 445–59

- [57] Mattoon E R, Cordero R J B and Casadevall A 2021 Fungal melanins and applications in healthcare, bioremediation and industry. *J Fungi (Basel)* **7**
- [58] Singla S, Htut K Z, Zhu R, Davis A, Ma J, Ni Q Z, Burkart M D, Maurer C, Miyoshi T and Dhinojwala A 2021 Isolation and Characterization of Allomelanin from Pathogenic Black Knot Fungus-a Sustainable Source of Melanin. *ACS Omega* **6** 35514–22
- [59] Varga M, Berkesi O, Darula Z, May N V and Palágyi A 2016 Structural characterization of allomelanin from black oat. *Phytochemistry* **130** 313–20
- [60] Singh S, Nimse S B, Mathew D E, Dhimmar A, Sahastrabudhe H, Gajjar A, Ghadge V A, Kumar P and Shinde P B 2021 Microbial melanin: Recent advances in biosynthesis, extraction, characterization, and applications. *Biotechnol. Adv.* **53** 107773
- [61] Styczynski M, Rogowska A, Nyabayo C, Decewicz P, Romaniuk F, Pączkowski C, Szakiel A, Suessmuth R and Dziewit L 2022 Heterologous production and characterization of a pyomelanin of Antarctic *Pseudomonas* sp. ANT_H4: a metabolite protecting against UV and free radicals, interacting with iron from minerals and exhibiting priming properties toward plant hairy roots. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **21** 261
- [62] Lorquin F, Piccerelle P, Orneto C, Robin M and Lorquin J 2022 New insights and advances on pyomelanin production: from microbial synthesis to applications. *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **49**
- [63] Lorquin F, Ziarelli F, Amouric A, Di Giorgio C, Robin M, Piccerelle P and Lorquin J 2021 Production and properties of non-cytotoxic pyomelanin by laccase and comparison to bacterial and synthetic pigments. *Sci. Rep.* **11** 8538
- [64] Roldan-Kalil J, Zueva L, Alves J, Tsytsarev V, Sanabria P and Inyushin M 2023 Amount of melanin granules in human hair defines the absorption and conversion to heat of light energy in the visible spectrum. *Photochem. Photobiol.* **99** 1092–6
- [65] Zhang G, Liu X, Xie W, Hong C, Xu Y, Zhang W, Zhao S, Xin H and Wang X 2021 Trash to treasure: A human beard derived photothermal drug delivery platform for depression therapy *Applied Materials Today* **22** 100891
- [66] Battistella C, McCallum N C, Gnanasekaran K, Zhou X, Caponetti V, Montalti M and Gianneschi N C 2020 Mimicking Natural Human Hair Pigmentation with Synthetic Melanin. *ACS Cent. Sci.* **6** 1179–88
- [67] Xie W, Yan F, Pakdel E, Sharp J, Liu D, Wang X, Zhan S and Sun L 2020 Natural Melanin/Polyurethane Composites as Highly Efficient Near-Infrared-Photoresponsive Shape Memory Implants. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **6** 5305–14
- [68] Liang Y, Han Q, Byrne N, Sun L and Wang X 2018 Recyclable One-Step Extraction and Characterization of Intact Melanin from Alpaca Fibers *Fibers Polym.* **19** 1640–6
- [69] Derby C D 2014 Cephalopod ink: production, chemistry, functions and applications. *Mar. Drugs* **12** 2700–30
- [70] Binsi P K, Muhamed Ashraf P, Parvathy U and Zynudheen A A 2022 Photo-protective effect of cuttlefish ink melanin on human hair *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **139**
- [71] Xie J, Li H, Che H, Dong X, Yang X and Xie W 2021 Extraction, physicochemical characterisation, and bioactive properties of ink melanin from cuttlefish (*Sepia esculenta*) *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* **56** 3627–40

- [72] Abidin F, Sulmartiwi L and Saputra E 2021 Characteristics physicochemical of melanin from squid ink (*Ioligo* sp.) extracted by ethanol *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* **679** 012038
- [73] PHUA J W and OTTENHEIM C J H 2021 A METHOD FOR OBTAINING MELANIN FROM INVERTEBRATE BIOMASS AND THE PRODUCT OBTAINED THEREFROM
- [74] Chen Y, Guo Y, He X, Tan B, Liao Z, Chen A, Gu X, Li X, Chen X, Chen B, Lin S, Li W, Hu P, Zhu X, Zhao W and Niu J 2025 Comprehensive utilization of black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*) larvae: extraction, recovery and characterization of peptide, chitin and melanin and scaling-up trial *Separation and Purification Technology* **361** 131262
- [75] Zhang L, Martin A, Perry M W, van der Burg K R L, Matsuoka Y, Monteiro A and Reed R D 2017 Genetic basis of melanin pigmentation in butterfly wings. *Genetics* **205** 1537–50
- [76] Jeon D-J, Paik S, Ji S and Yeo J-S 2021 Melanin-based structural coloration of birds and its biomimetic applications. *AM* **51** 14
- [77] Lee E, Tanaka H, Wakamatsu K and Sugita S 2009 Melanin-based iridescent feather color in the Jungle Crow. *J. Vet. Med. Sci.* **71** 1261–3
- [78] Edwards N P, van Veelen A, Anné J, Manning P L, Bergmann U, Sellers W I, Egerton V M, Sokaras D, Alonso-Mori R, Wakamatsu K, Ito S and Wogelius R A 2016 Elemental characterisation of melanin in feathers via synchrotron X-ray imaging and absorption spectroscopy. *Sci. Rep.* **6** 34002
- [79] Kalinina S N, Ilyukha V A, Uzenbaeva L B, Antonova Ye P, Bruler Ye S and Okulova I I 2021 Melanin in the pineal gland of species in the family canidae *Neurosci. Behav. Physiol.* **51** 1312–6
- [80] Alam M Z, Ramachandran T, Antony A, Hamed F, Ayyash M and Kamal-Eldin A 2022 Melanin is a plenteous bioactive phenolic compound in date fruits (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.). *Sci. Rep.* **12** 6614
- [81] Wang L-F and Rhim J-W 2019 Isolation and characterization of melanin from black garlic and sepia ink *LWT* **99** 17–23
- [82] Aghajanyan A E, Hambardzumyan A A, Minasyan E V, Hovhannisyan G J, Yeghiyan K I, Soghomonian T M, Avetisyan S V, Sakanyan V A and Tsaturyan A H 2024 Efficient isolation and characterization of functional melanin from various plant sources *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* **59** 3545–55
- [83] Aghajanyan A E, Hambardzumyan A A, Minasyan E V, Tsaturyan A H, Paloyan A M, Avetisyan S V, Hovsepyan A S and Saghyan A S 2022 Development of the technology for producing water-soluble melanin from waste of vinary production and the study of its physicochemical properties *Eur. Food Res. Technol.* **248** 485–95
- [84] Glagoleva A Y, Shoeva O Y and Khlestkina E K 2020 Melanin pigment in plants: current knowledge and future perspectives. *Front. Plant Sci.* **11** 770
- [85] Filatova A V, Azimova L B, Djurabaev D T, Radjabov O I, Otajonov A Yu and Yakubova R A 2024 Technology for obtaining melanin from the shells of horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum* L.), studying its composition *BIO Web of Conferences* **113** 03001
- [86] Dossou S S K, Luo Z, Wang Z, Zhou W, Zhou R, Zhang Y, Li D, Liu A, Dossa K, You J and Wang L 2022 The Dark Pigment in the Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) Seed Coat: Isolation, Characterization, and Its Potential Precursors. *Front. Nutr.* **9** 858673

- [87] Popov V S, Korniyukhin D L, Shelengaf T V, Gavrilova V A and Khoreva V I 2025 Determination of allomelanins in sunflower husk by the gravimetric method *Plant Breed. Biotech* **8** 23–32
- [88] Sunil Kumar B T, Sathyendra Rao B V, Swathi S, Vanajakshi V, Hebbar H U and Singh S A 2024 Characterization, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activity of melanin extracted from nigerseed hulls *Food Biosci.* **61** 104929
- [89] Łopusiewicz Ł, Drożdowska E, Trocer P, Kostek M, Śliwiński M, Henriques M H F, Bartkowiak A and Sobolewski P 2020 Whey Protein Concentrate/Isolate Biofunctional Films Modified with Melanin from Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) Seeds. *Materials (Basel)* **13**
- [90] Suthar M, Dufossé L and Singh S K 2023 The enigmatic world of fungal melanin: A comprehensive review. *J Fungi (Basel)* **9**
- [91] Suwannarach N, Kumla J, Watanabe B, Matsui K and Lumyong S 2019 Characterization of melanin and optimal conditions for pigment production by an endophytic fungus, *Spissiomycetes endophytica* SDBR-CMU319. *PLoS ONE* **14** e0222187
- [92] Lu M, Yu M, Shi T, Ma J, Fu X, Meng X and Shi L 2020 Optimization of ultrasound-assisted extraction of melanin and its hypoglycemic activities from *Sporisorium reilianum* *J. Food Process. Preserv.* **44**
- [93] Zhang Y, Wu X, Huang C, Zhang Z and Gao W 2022 Isolation and identification of pigments from oyster mushrooms with black, yellow and pink caps. *Food Chem.* **372** 131171
- [94] Ribera J, Panzarasa G, Stobbe A, Osypova A, Rupper P, Klose D and Schwarze F W M R 2019 Scalable Biosynthesis of Melanin by the Basidiomycete *Armillaria cepistipes*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **67** 132–9
- [95] Kalaiselvam M, Thangavelu R and Michael H S R 2013 Production and Characterization of Melanin Pigment from Halophilic Black Yeast *Hortaea werneckii* *International Journal of Pharma Research & Review* **2** 9–17
- [96] Pandey S, Meshram V, Yehia H M, Alzahrani A, Akhtar N and Sur A 2023 Efficient production and characterization of melanin from *Thermothelomyces hinnuleus* SP1, isolated from the coal mines of Chhattisgarh, India. *Front. Microbiol.* **14** 1320116
- [97] A.S. D, Tinu T, Nisha J, Akkumol S and Preetha K 2024 Isolation and Characterization of Melanin from the Commercially Available Edible Mushrooms *Kavaka* **60** 21–5
- [98] Choi K-Y 2021 Bioprocess of microbial melanin production and isolation. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **9** 765110
- [99] Guo J, Rao Z, Yang T, Man Z, Xu M and Zhang X 2014 High-level production of melanin by a novel isolate of *Streptomyces kathirae*. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **357** 85–91
- [100] Ganesh Kumar C, Sahu N, Narendra Reddy G, Prasad R B N, Nagesh N and Kamal A 2013 Production of melanin pigment from *Pseudomonas stutzeri* isolated from red seaweed *Hypnea musciformis*. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.* **57** 295–302
- [101] Tarangini K and Mishra S 2014 Production of melanin by soil microbial isolate on fruit waste extract: two step optimization of key parameters. *Biotechnol Rep (Amst)* **4** 139–46
- [102] Seo D and Choi K-Y 2020 Heterologous production of pyomelanin biopolymer using 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate dioxygenase isolated from *Ralstonia pickettii* in *Escherichia coli* *Biochem. Eng. J.* **157** 107548

- [103] Chen M, Guo B, Cheng H, Wang W, Jin J, Zhang Y, Deng X, Yang W, Wu C, Gao X, Yu D, Feng W and Chen Y 2024 Genetic Engineering *Bacillus thuringiensis* Enable Melanin Biosynthesis for Anti-Tumor and Anti-Inflammation *Adv. Sci.*
- [104] K Kurian N 2024 Extraction and Purification of Melanin from Different Sources and Tissues *Exon 1*
- [105] Pralea I-E, Moldovan R-C, Petrache A-M, Ilieş M, Hegheş S-C, Ielciu I, Nicoară R, Moldovan M, Ene M, Radu M, Uifălean A and Iuga C-A 2019 From extraction to advanced analytical methods: the challenges of melanin analysis. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **20**
- [106] Aghajanyan A, Minasyan E, Soghomonyan T, Melyan G, Hovhannisyan G, Yeghiyan K, Karapetyan K and Tsaturyan A 2025 Isolation, purification, identification of melanin from grape pomace extracts, and its application areas *BCHD* **8** 204–16
- [107] Song W, Xing R, Yang H, Liu S and Li P 2021 Optimization of extractions of eumelanin from cuttlefish ink and the hypoglycemic effects: In vitro enzyme inhibitory activity and glucose consumption in HepG2 cells *J. Food Process. Preserv.* **45**
- [108] Song W, Xing R, Yang H, Gao K, Liu S, Li X, Yu H and Li P 2023 Eumelanin: A natural antioxidant isolated from squid ink by new enzymatic technique and prediction of its structural tetramer *LWT* **188** 115464
- [109] Song W, Xing R, Yang H, Liu S, Yu H and Li P 2024 Therapeutic potential of enzymatically extracted eumelanin from squid ink in type 2 diabetes mellitus ICR mice: Multifaceted intervention against hyperglycemia, oxidative stress and depression *J. Sci. Food Agric.* **104** 993–1007
- [110] Ghadge V, Kumar P, Maity T K, Prasad K and Shinde P B 2022 Facile alternative sustainable process for the selective extraction of microbial melanin *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **10** 2681–8
- [111] Singh N and Prasad K 2019 Multi-tasking hydrated ionic liquids as sustainable media for the processing of waste human hair: a biorefinery approach *Green Chem.* **21** 3328–33
- [112] Mukherjee A, Pal S, Parhi S, Karki S, Ingole P G and Ghosh P 2023 One-Pot Extraction of Bioresources from Human Hair via a Zero-Waste Green Route. *ACS Omega* **8** 15759–68
- [113] Kumar K, Srivastav S and Sharanagat V S 2021 Ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE) of bioactive compounds from fruit and vegetable processing by-products: A review. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* **70** 105325
- [114] Shen L, Pang S, Zhong M, Sun Y, Qayum A, Liu Y, Rashid A, Xu B, Liang Q, Ma H and Ren X 2023 A comprehensive review of ultrasonic assisted extraction (UAE) for bioactive components: Principles, advantages, equipment, and combined technologies. *Ultrason. Sonochem.* **101** 106646
- [115] Hou R, Liu X, Xiang K, Chen L, Wu X, Lin W, Zheng M and Fu J 2019 Characterization of the physicochemical properties and extraction optimization of natural melanin from *Inonotus hispidus* mushroom. *Food Chem.* **277** 533–42
- [116] Hamid Nour A, Ruth Oluwaseun A, Hamid Nour A, Suliman Omer M and Ahmed N 2021 Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Bioactive Compounds (Review) *Microwave Heating - Electromagnetic Fields Causing Thermal and Non-Thermal Effects* ed G I. Churyumov (IntechOpen)

- [117] Louis A, Chich J F, Chepca H, Schmitz I, Hugueney P and Maia-Grondard A 2025 Green Extraction Method: Microwave-Assisted Water Extraction Followed by HILIC-HRMS Analysis to Quantify Hydrophilic Compounds in Plants. *Metabolites* **15**
- [118] Lu Y, Ye M, Song S, Li L, Shaikh F and Li J 2014 Isolation, purification, and anti-aging activity of melanin from *Lachnum singerianum*. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* **174** 762–71
- [119] Ma Y, Zhang P, Dai X, Yao X, Zhou S, Ma Q, Liu J, Tian S, Zhu J, Zhang J, Kong X and Bao Y 2023 Extraction, physicochemical properties, and antioxidant activity of natural melanin from *Auricularia heimuer* fermentation. *Front. Nutr.* **10** 1131542
- [120] Ghadge V, Kumar P, Maity T K, Prasad K and Shinde P B 2021 A facile alternative sustainable process for the extraction and purification of microbial melanin *BioRxiv*
- [121] Chen S-R, Jiang B, Zheng J-X, Xu G-Y, Li J-Y and Yang N 2008 Isolation and characterization of natural melanin derived from silky fowl (*Gallus gallus domesticus* Brisson) *Food Chem.* **111** 745–9
- [122] Liu Y, Kempf V R, Nofsinger J B, Weinert E E, Rudnicki M, Wakamatsu K, Ito S and Simon J D 2003 Comparison of the structural and physical properties of human hair eumelanin following enzymatic or acid/base extraction. *Pigment Cell Res.* **16** 355–65
- [123] Lazić V, Klaus A, Kozarski M, Doroški A, Tosti T, Simić S and Vunduk J 2024 The effect of green extraction technologies on the chemical composition of medicinal chaga mushroom extracts. *J Fungi (Basel)* **10**
- [124] Al-Ajalein A-H A S, Shafie M H, Yap P-G, Kassim M A, Naharudin I, Wong T-W and Gan C-Y 2023 Microwave-assisted extraction of polysaccharide from *Cinnamomum cassia* with anti-hyperpigmentation properties: Optimization and characterization studies *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **226** 321–35
- [125] Luo F, Liu Z and Chen Z 2023 Ionic liquid as regenerable media for simultaneous recovery of melanin and amino acid from waste human hair: An elaborate and efficient biorefining approach *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy* **35** 101219
- [126] Mustakim Z, Prasetya A, Wintoko J and Purnomo C W 2024 Review on melanin application as an antibacterial and antioxidant agent in food packaging *Indones. J. Chem.* **24** 1906
- [127] El-Naggar N E-A and El-Ewasy S M 2017 Bioproduction, characterization, anticancer and antioxidant activities of extracellular melanin pigment produced by newly isolated microbial cell factories *Streptomyces glaucescens* NEAE-H. *Sci. Rep.* **7** 42129
- [128] Arun and Kumar P 2020 Antioxidant activity of melanin free ink (MFI) extract from the ink sac of *Loligo duvauceli*
- [129] Shaju P M, Ganesan P, Kingston S D and Muruganantham M 2022 Fourier transform Infrared characterization of melanin free ink from selected cephalopods for identification of active functional groups responsible for antioxidant activity *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* **99** 100375
- [130] Le T-K, Lai S-Y, Huang Y-W, Chen Y-T, Hou C-Y and Hsieh S-L 2024 Antioxidant activity and mechanism of melanin from cuttlefish (*Sepia pharaonis*) ink on Clone-9 cells *Food Biosci.* **60** 104444
- [131] Fu X, Xie M, Lu M, Shi L, Shi T and Yu M 2022 Characterization of the physicochemical properties, antioxidant activity, and antiproliferative activity of natural melanin from *S. reiliana*. *Sci. Rep.* **12** 2110

- [132] Sheefaa M I and Sivaperumal P 2022 Antioxidant activities from melanin pigment produced by marine actinobacterium of *Streptomyces* species *J. Adv. Pharm. Technol. Res.* **13** S84–7
- [133] Simon J D, Peles D, Wakamatsu K and Ito S 2009 Current challenges in understanding melanogenesis: bridging chemistry, biological control, morphology, and function. *Pigment Cell Melanoma Res.* **22** 563–79
- [134] Polapally R, Mansani M, Rajkumar K, Burgula S, Hameeda B, Alhazmi A, Bantun F, Almalki A H, Haque S, El Enshasy H A and Sayyed R Z 2022 Melanin pigment of *Streptomyces puniceus* RHPR9 exhibits antibacterial, antioxidant and anticancer activities. *PLoS ONE* **17** e0266676
- [135] Barretto D A and Vootla S K 2020 Biological activities of melanin pigment extracted from *Bombyx mori* gut-associated yeast *Cryptococcus rajasthanensis* KY627764. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **36** 159
- [136] Zu Z, Sheng J, Qi J, Miao Y, Zhang Y, Zheng T, Xiang K, Wu H, Lu G and Zhang L 2023 Natural cell patches: melanin nanoparticles for MR imaging-guided antiatherosclerosis therapy via attenuating macrophage pyroptosis *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **33**
- [137] Zhou J, Liu W, Zhao X, Xian Y, Wu W, Zhang X, Zhao N, Xu F-J and Wang C 2021 Natural Melanin/Alginate Hydrogels Achieve Cardiac Repair through ROS Scavenging and Macrophage Polarization. *Adv Sci (Weinh)* **8** e2100505
- [138] Liu L, Lu K, Xie J, Che H, Li H and Wancui X 2023 Melanin from *Sepia pharaonis* ink alleviates mucosal damage and reduces inflammation to prevent alcohol-induced gastric ulcers *Food Biosci.* **51** 102266
- [139] Abd-El-Aziz A S, Abed N N, Mahfouz A Y and Fathy R M 2024 Production and characterization of melanin pigment from black fungus *Curvularia soli* AS21 ON076460 assisted gamma rays for promising medical uses. *Microb. Cell Fact.* **23** 68
- [140] Seelam S D, Agsar D, Halmuthur M S K, Reddy Shetty P, Vemireddy S, Reddy K M, Umesh M K and Rajitha C H 2021 Characterization and photoprotective potentiality of lime dwelling *Pseudomonas* mediated melanin as sunscreen agent against UV-B radiations. *J Photochem Photobiol B, Biol* **216** 112126
- [141] Le T N, Tran N T H, Pham V N T, Van-Thi N-D and Tran H T M 2023 Anti-ultraviolet, antibacterial, and biofilm eradication activities against *Cutibacterium acnes* of melanins and melanin derivatives from *Daedaleopsis tricolor* and *Fomes fomentarius*. *Front. Microbiol.* **14** 1305778
- [142] Kotakonda M, Marappan M and Biswas B 2024 Characterization and Antibacterial Activity of Melanin Pigment from Marine Bacterium *Actinoalloteichus cyanogriseus* Lett. *Drug Des. Discov.* **21** 938–47
- [143] Fitriah Y and Khusnul Khotimah I 2021 The Antibacterial Activity of Melanin in the Cuttlefish (*Sepia* sp.) Ink against *Aeromonas* sp. *Egypt. J. of Aquatic Biolo. and Fish.* **25** 689–704
- [144] Łopusiewicz Ł 2018 Antioxidant, antibacterial properties and the lightbarrier assessment of raw and purified melanins isolated from *Citrullus lanatus* (watermelon) seeds *Herba Pol* **64** 25–36
- [145] Kim E, Panzella L, Napolitano A and Payne G F 2020 Redox Activities of Melanins Investigated by Electrochemical Reverse Engineering: Implications for their Roles in Oxidative Stress. *J. Invest. Dermatol.* **140** 537–43

- [146] Xu Z, Chen Z, Wang W, Meng X, Wang X, Xia Y, Meng Q, Li Y, Song R and Chen G 2024 Cuttlefish ink-derived melanin nanoparticle-embedded tremella fuciformis polysaccharide hydrogels for the treatment of MRSA-infected diabetic wounds. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **277** 134342
- [147] Liang Y, Zhao Y, Sun H, Dan J, Kang Y, Zhang Q, Su Z, Ni Y, Shi S, Wang J and Zhang W 2023 Natural melanin nanoparticle-based photothermal film for edible antibacterial food packaging. *Food Chem.* **401** 134117
- [148] Montefiori D C and Zhou J 1991 Selective antiviral activity of synthetic soluble l-tyrosine and l-dopa melanins against human immunodeficiency virus in vitro *Antiviral Res.* **15** 11–25
- [149] Rajaganapathi J, Thyagarajan S P and Edward J K 2000 Study on cephalopod's ink for anti-retroviral activity. *Indian J. Exp. Biol.* **38** 519–20
- [150] Vijayababu P and Kurian N K 2021 Melanin and its Precursors as Effective Antiviral Compounds: with a Special Focus on SARS CoV2 *Mol Biol (NY)* **10**
- [151] Koch S M, Freidank-Pohl C, Siontas O, Cortesao M, Mota A, Runzheimer K, Jung S, Rebrosova K, Siler M, Moeller R and Meyer V 2023 *Aspergillus niger* as a cell factory for the production of pyomelanin, a molecule with UV-C radiation shielding activity. *Front. Microbiol.* **14** 1233740
- [152] Zhdanova N N, Zakharchenko V A, Vember V V and Nakonechnaya L T 2000 Fungi from Chernobyl: mycobiota of the inner regions of the containment structures of the damaged nuclear reactor *Mycol. Res.* **104** 1421–6
- [153] Dadachova E, Bryan R A, Howell R C, Schweitzer A D, Aisen P, Nosanchuk J D and Casadevall A 2008 The radioprotective properties of fungal melanin are a function of its chemical composition, stable radical presence and spatial arrangement. *Pigment Cell Melanoma Res.* **21** 192–9
- [154] Revskaya E, Chu P, Howell R C, Schweitzer A D, Bryan R A, Harris M, Gerfen G, Jiang Z, Jandl T, Kim K, Ting L-M, Sellers R S, Dadachova E and Casadevall A 2012 Compton scattering by internal shields based on melanin-containing mushrooms provides protection of gastrointestinal tract from ionizing radiation. *Cancer Biother. Radiopharm.* **27** 570–6
- [155] Kunal S, Bhanushali S, Raghukumar S and Dadachova E 2025 Melanin from the fungus *Gliocephalotrichum simplex* protects seeds from the effects of exposure to gamma radiation. *Sci. Rep.* **15** 6473
- [156] Nguyen Thi L N, Le Duc S, Bui Thi V K, Dinh Thi T T, Do Xuan H, Hoang Thi M N and Nguyen Dinh T 2022 Protective effect of melanin nanoparticles created from squid ink against irradiation on human keratinocytes *J. Nanostruct. Chem.*
- [157] Luo Z, Bian F, Cao X, Shang L, Zhao Y and Bi Y 2024 Bio-inspired self-adhesive microparticles with melanin nanoparticles integration for wound closure and healing *Nano Today* **54** 102138
- [158] Zeng Q, Peng Q, Wang F, Shi G, Haick H and Zhang M 2023 Tailoring Food Biopolymers into Biogels for Regenerative Wound Healing and Versatile Skin Bioelectronics. *Nano-Micro Lett.* **15** 153
- [159] Hao Z, Zhang F, Chen L, Zhang H, Pang H, Liu W, Liu J, Zhang R, Li X and Zhang L 2025 Marine-inspired near-infrared-activated multifunctional hydrogel with immunomodulatory properties for multidrug-resistant bacterial infected wound healing. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **693** 137562

- [160] Song J, Geng Z, Luan X, Zhang D, Wang Q, Pan L, Yu X, Dong W, Wu D and You S 2024 Construction of natural hydrogels consisting of oxidized dextran, quaternized chitosan and cuttlefish ink nanoparticles for treating diabetic oral ulcers. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **283** 137737
- [161] Liu Y M, Ma W S, Wei Y X and Xu Y H 2020 Photothermal Effect-based Cytotoxic Ability of Melanin from *Mytilus edulis* Shells to Heal Wounds Infected with Drug-resistant Bacteria in vivo. *Biomed. Environ. Sci.* **33** 471–83
- [162] Taburets O V, Morgaienko O O, Kondratiuk T O, Beregova T V and Ostapchenko L I 2016 The Effect of “Melanin-Gel” on the Wound Healing *Res J Pharm Biol Chem Sci* **7** 2031–8
- [163] Janahmadi Z, Momeni S, Manoochehri H and Talebi S 2024 Development of an efficient hemostatic material based on cuttlefish ink nanoparticles loaded in cuttlebone biocomposite. *J. Mater. Chem. B Mater. Biol. Med.* **12** 4172–83
- [164] D’Amora U, Soriente A, Ronca A, Scialla S, Perrella M, Manini P, Phua J W, Ottenheim C, Di Girolamo R, Pezzella A, Raucci M G and Ambrosio L 2022 Eumelanin from the Black Soldier Fly as Sustainable Biomaterial: Characterisation and Functional Benefits in Tissue-Engineered Composite Scaffolds. *Biomedicines* **10**
- [165] Huang M, Zhang L, Cui J, Zhang M, Wang Z, Yu S, Du F, An Z, Xu L and Cao J 2025 3D printing of GelMA/nanohydroxyapatite/melanin nanoparticles composite hydrogel scaffolds for bone regeneration through immunomodulation. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **306** 141453
- [166] Umur E, Arslan F, Bakay E, Sirek B, Ayan B, Baysoy E, Topaloğlu N and Kaleli-Can G 2024 Layer-by-layer assembled melanin nanoparticles thin films for photodynamic activity-based disinfection by ultraviolet A irradiation *emergent mater.* **7** 2547–62
- [167] García-García M, Orona-Tamayo D, Estrada-Monje A, Quintana-Rodríguez E, Navarro-Mendoza R, Hernández-Perales L, Lozoya-Perez N E and Jaime-Ferrer J S 2025 Melanin from Pecan Nut Shell Waste as an Antioxidant and Antifungal Additive in Membranes for Food Packaging *J. Polym. Environ.* **33** 1469–90
- [168] García-García M, Jaime-Ferrer J S, Medrano-Lango F N, Quintana-Rodríguez E, Campos-García T, Rodríguez-Sevilla E and Orona-Tamayo D 2025 Electrospun Membranes Loaded with Melanin Derived from Pecan Nutshell (*Carya illinoensis*) Residues for Skin-Care Applications. *Membranes (Basel)* **15**
- [169] Guo H, Cao Z, Li J, Fu Z, Lin S, Wang L and Liu J 2023 Integrating Bacteria with a Ternary Combination of Photosensitizers for Monochromatic Irradiation-Mediated Photoacoustic Imaging-Guided Synergistic Photothermal Therapy. *ACS Nano* **17** 5059–71
- [170] Kim M, Kim H S, Kim M A, Ryu H, Jeong H-J and Lee C-M 2017 Thermohydrogel containing melanin for photothermal cancer therapy. *Macromol. Biosci.* **17**
- [171] Lei Q, He D, Ding L, Kong F, He P, Huang J, Guo J, Brinker C J, Luo G, Zhu W and Yu Y 2022 Microneedle Patches Integrated with Biomineralized Melanin Nanoparticles for Simultaneous Skin Tumor Photothermal Therapy and Wound Healing *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **32**
- [172] Jia J, Guo X, Wang Y, Wu M, Wang X, Zhao M and Zhao Y 2024 Living photosynthetic microneedle patches for in situ oxygenation and postsurgical melanoma therapy. *J. Nanobiotechnology* **22** 698
- [173] Dong J, Sun J, Cai W, Guo C, Wang Q, Zhao X and Zhang R 2022 A natural cuttlefish melanin nanoprobe for preoperative and intraoperative mapping of lymph nodes. *Nanomedicine* **41** 102510

- [174] Chu M, Hai W, Zhang Z, Wo F, Wu Q, Zhang Z, Shao Y, Zhang D, Jin L and Shi D 2016 Melanin nanoparticles derived from a homology of medicine and food for sentinel lymph node mapping and photothermal in vivo cancer therapy. *Biomaterials* **91** 182–99
- [175] Hu Y, Xue S, Long T, Lyu P, Zhang X, Chen J, Chen S, Liu C and Chen X 2020 Opto-acoustic synergistic irradiation for vaporization of natural melanin-cored nanodroplets at safe energy levels and efficient sono-chemo-photothermal cancer therapy. *Theranostics* **10** 10448–65
- [176] Soltani S, Roy A, Urtti A and Karttunen M 2024 A computational investigation of eumelanin–drug binding in aqueous solutions *Mater. Adv.* **5** 5494–513
- [177] Caldas M, Barbosa A I, Bhattacharya M, Reis R L and Correlo V M 2024 Natural melanin nanoparticles (MNPs) extracted from *Sepia officinalis*: A cost-effective, chemo-photothermal, synergistic nanopatform for osteosarcoma treatment. *Colloids Surf. B Biointerfaces* **239** 113937
- [178] Caldas M, Santos A C, Rebelo R, Pereira I, Veiga F, Reis R L and Correlo V M 2020 Electro-responsive controlled drug delivery from melanin nanoparticles. *Int. J. Pharm.* **588** 119773
- [179] Gao L, Yang L, Guo L, Wang H, Zhao Y, Xie J and Shi N 2022 Improving the solubility of melanin nanoparticles from apricot kernels is a potent drug delivery system *J. Appl. Biomater. Funct. Mater.* **20**
- [180] Xiao Y, Zhang S, Zhuo H, Zhang X, Zhu K, Chen W, You G, Chen H, Luo Q, Zhou H and Chen G 2025 Dietary natural melanin nanozymes delay aging and ameliorate neurodegeneration via improving gut microbiota and redox homeostasis. *ACS Omega* **10** 3610–21
- [181] Xie J, Liu L, Guo H, Bao Q, Hu P, Li H, Che H and Xie W 2022 Orally administered melanin from *Sepiapharaonis* ink ameliorates depression-anxiety-like behaviors in DSS-induced colitis by mediating inflammation pathway and regulating apoptosis. *Int. Immunopharmacol.* **106** 108625
- [182] Hou R, Liu X, Wu X, Zheng M and Fu J 2021 Therapeutic effect of natural melanin from edible fungus *Auricularia auricula* on alcohol-induced liver damage in vitro and in vivo *Food Science and Human Wellness* **10** 514–22
- [183] Yang Z, Zhang J, Liu H, Hu J, Wang X, Bai W, Zhang W, Yang Y, Gu Z and Li Y 2023 A Bioinspired Strategy Toward UV Absorption Enhancement of Melanin-like Polymers for Sun Protection *CCS Chem.* **5** 2389–402
- [184] Brenner M and Hearing V J 2008 The protective role of melanin against UV damage in human skin. *Photochem. Photobiol.* **84** 539–49
- [185] Zamudio Díaz D F, Busch L, Kröger M, Klein A L, Lohan S B, Mewes K R, Vierkotten L, Witzel C, Rohn S and Meinke M C 2024 Significance of melanin distribution in the epidermis for the protective effect against UV light. *Sci. Rep.* **14** 3488
- [186] ElObeid A S, Kamal-Eldin A, Abdelhalim M A K and Haseeb A M 2017 Pharmacological properties of melanin and its function in health. *Basic Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* **120** 515–22
- [187] Gao J, Wenderoth M, Doppler M, Schuhmacher R, Marko D and Fischer R 2022 Fungal melanin biosynthesis pathway as source for fungal toxins. *MBio* **13** e0021922

- [188] Krutmann J, Piquero-Casals J, Morgado-Carrasco D, Granger C, Trullàs C, Passeron T and Lim H W 2023 Photoprotection for people with skin of colour: needs and strategies. *Br. J. Dermatol.* **188** 168–75
- [189] Zhang X, Tao H, Zhang Z, Wang W, Steel A, Fang X and He X 2024 Evaluation of the efficacy of a sunscreen containing ultra-long UVA1 and other UVR broad-spectrum filters on skin barrier protection and melanin content reduction in Chinese adults: A single-center study. *Health Sci. Rep.* **7** e1923
- [190] Geng J, Tang W, Wan X, Zhou Q, Wang X J, Shen P, Lei T C and Chen X D 2008 Photoprotection of bacterial-derived melanin against ultraviolet A-induced cell death and its potential application as an active sunscreen. *J. Eur. Acad. Dermatol. Venereol.* **22** 852–8
- [191] Anon Creanatural® Sepia Melanin
- [192] Anon Creanatural® Vegetable Melanin
- [193] Anon SPF 50+ cream with melanin Glow On
- [194] Huang L, Liu M, Huang H, Wen Y, Zhang X and Wei Y 2018 Recent Advances and Progress on Melanin-like Materials and Their Biomedical Applications. *Biomacromolecules* **19** 1858–68
- [195] Magarelli M, Passamonti P and Renieri C 2010 Purification, characterization and analysis of sepia melanin from commercial sepia ink (*Sepia Officinalis*) *Revista CES Medicina Veterinaria y Zootecnia*
- [196] Cavallini C, Vitiello G, Adinolfi B, Silvestri B, Armanetti P, Manini P, Pezzella A, d’Ischia M, Luciani G and Menichetti L 2020 Melanin and Melanin-Like Hybrid Materials in Regenerative Medicine. *Nanomaterials (Basel)* **10**
- [197] Omidian H and Wilson R L 2024 Polydopamine applications in biomedicine and environmental science. *Materials (Basel)* **17**
- [198] Sava V M, Hung Y C, Blagodarsky V A, Hong M Y and Huang G S 2003 The liver-protecting activity of melanin-like pigment derived from black tea *Food Res. Int* **36** 505–11
- [199] Drewnowska J M, Zambrzycka M, Kalska-Szostko B, Fiedoruk K and Swiecicka I 2015 Melanin-Like Pigment Synthesis by Soil *Bacillus weihenstephanensis* Isolates from Northeastern Poland. *PLoS ONE* **10** e0125428
- [200] Sava V M, Galkin B N, Hong M-Y, Yang P-C and Huang G S 2001 A novel melanin-like pigment derived from black tea leaves with immuno-stimulating activity *Food Res. Int* **34** 337–43
- [201] Choudhury A and Ghosh D 2025 Elucidating the Structure of Melanin and Its Structure-Property Correlation. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **58** 1509–18
- [202] Ghadge V, Kumar P, Singh S, Mathew D E, Bhattacharya S, Nimse S B and Shinde P B 2020 Natural Melanin Produced by the Endophytic *Bacillus subtilis* 4NP-BL Associated with the Halophyte *Salicornia brachiata*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **68** 6854–63
- [203] Prados-Rosales R, Toriola S, Nakouzi A, Chatterjee S, Stark R, Gerfen G, Tumpowsky P, Dadachova E and Casadevall A 2015 Structural Characterization of Melanin Pigments from Commercial Preparations of the Edible Mushroom *Auricularia auricula*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **63** 7326–32

- [204] Muñoz-Torres P, Cárdenas-Ninasivincha S and Aguilar Y 2024 Exploring the agricultural applications of microbial melanin. *Microorganisms* **12**
- [205] Asah-Asante R, Tang L, Gong X, Fan S, Yan C, Asante J O and Zeng Q 2025 Exploring pigment-producing *Streptomyces* as an alternative source to synthetic pigments: diversity, biosynthesis, and biotechnological applications. A review. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **41** 211
- [206] Zhang C, Zhao X, Guo S, Lin T and Guo H 2017 Highly effective photothermal chemotherapy with pH-responsive polymer-coated drug-loaded melanin-like nanoparticles. *Int. J. Nanomedicine* **12** 1827–40